

Forearm and Lower Limb Golf Swing Assessments Using Techniques of
Electromyography and Kinematics.

By

Mr Henry Hunter, BSc

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Abstract

Context: This thesis focuses on validation of three main computer assisted systems that can be attributed to golf performance and injury prevention (wrist, elbow, hip, knee and ankle). Technologies from Myon, Vicon, Kinovea, and Siliconcoach will be used to gather electromyographic (EMG), video and kinematic data to validate the equipment and protocols used within these studies and also highlight the effects that these trials may help improve injury prevention and performance.

Aims: Firstly, to measure, collect and analyse the electrical muscle signal output during five trials and determine the impact on hand morphology. Secondly, to validate a 2-Dimensional augmented video-based portable system (AVPS) against a gold standard 3-Dimensional motion analysis system and finally to use the gold standard Vicon system to investigate the changes in kinematic variables of the lower limbs before and during fatigue.

Method: All participants in the EMG study had no history of wrist or elbow injuries within a twelve-month period and no surgery in these areas over a five-year period. All golf study participants played golf regularly and had no injuries to the elbow, wrist or lower limbs. Surface electromyography (sEMG), kinematic and performance variables were collected simultaneously from each trial.

Results: The results from study one showed no significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) whilst comparing left and right flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS) or extensor carpi radialis brevis (ECRB). Secondary findings noted that whilst comparing the EMG output from the FDS and ECRB on the same arm, the ECRB displayed an average

of 3.3 times the output of the FDS ($SD \pm 0.49$). The second study showed no significant differences for swing time ($P = 0.763$, $F = 0.099$) with only the acceleration ($P = 0.018$, $F = 5.718$) golf phase measurement showing statistically significant differences between the 2D and 3D software comparisons. The results showed a high intra-class correlation coefficient ($ICC > 0.929$) and Cronbach's coefficient alpha ($CCA > 0.924$) reliability for both the kinematic and temporal parameters. Study three shows that although there is no significant difference displayed for the Y (lateral/medial) and Z (proximal/distal) axis of the right knee angle during all phases with both clubs, there are significant differences throughout the remainder of the swing/joint angles. This increases during the faster phases of the swing and/or with the shorter 7-iron club.

Conclusions: Research from these studies found that data from each of the trialled systems and processes were reliably evaluated for use within a golf related environment. Results from descriptive and inferential statistics have shown that these methods and systems outlined can be used reliably to assist with both biomechanical performance improvement as well as injury prevention. Further research may be required to analyse kinetic variables during the golf swing in both pre and post fatigue states. The author suggests that further investigations in this area on a golf course rather than a laboratory setting is required. Additional research has been planned to add to the current fatigue studies and analyse the effect that fatigue can have on the kinetic variables during the golf swing.

The findings demonstrate that the methods and systems outlined in this study can be used reliably in future research.

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Abbreviations and Units of Measurements

2D	- 2 Dimensional
3D	- 3 Dimensional
ACL	- Anterior Cruciate Ligament
ASIS	- Anterior Superior Iliac Spine
AVPS	- Augmented Video-Based Portable Systems
BCE	- Before Common Era
BF	- Biceps Femoris
CCA	- Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha
CHV	- Club Head Velocity
CMAS	- Clinical Movement Analysis Society of UK and Ireland
CV	- Coefficient of Variation
ECRB	- Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis
EMG	- Electromyography
FDS	- Flexor Digitorum Superficialis
GL	- Gastrocnemius Lateralis
GM	- Gluteus Maximus
GMED	- Gluteus Medius
GMED	- Gastrocnemius Medialis

GRF - Ground Reaction Force

Hz - Hertz

ICC - Intraclass Correlation Coefficient

KG - Kilograms

LGM - Lower Gluteus Maximus

LPSI - Left Posterior Superior Iliac Spine

M - Metres

MVC - Maximum Voluntary Contraction

MVC - Maximum Voluntary Contraction

PARQ - Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire

PL - Peroneus Longus

POSE - Position and Orientation of a Segment

PSIS - Posterior Super Iliac Spine

RF - Rectus Femoris

RMS - Root Means Squared

RPSI - Right Posterior Superior Iliac Spine

SD - Standard Deviation

SEM - Standard Error of Mean

sEMG - Surface Anterior Cruciate Ligament

SM - Standard Error of Measurement

SPSS - Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

ST - Semitendinosus

TL - Tibialis Anterior

UGM - Upper Gluteus Maximus

VL - Vastus Lateralis

VM - Vastus Medialis

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Peer Reviewed Publications

- a) An Electromyographic Study of the Effect of Hand Grip Sizes on Forearm Muscle Activity and Golf Performance. G. Sorbie, G., Hunter, H. H., Grace, F. M., Gu, Y., Baker, J. S. and Ugbolue, U. C., 2 Jul 2016, In: Research in Sports Medicine. 24, 3, p. 207-218 12 p.

- b) An Electromyographic Assessment Pilot Study on the Reliability of the Forearm Muscles During Multi-Planar Maximum Voluntary Contraction Grip and Wrist Articulation in Young Males. Hunter, H. H., Sorbie, G. G., Grace, F. M., Gu, Y., Lam, W-K., Baker, J. S., Dutheil, F., Dias, T. and Ugbolue, U. C., 12 May 2022, In: Technology and Health Care. 30, 3, p. 713-724 12 p., 212822.

- c) An Evaluation of Temporal and Club Angle Parameters During Golf Swings Using Low-Cost Video Analyses Packages. Hunter, H.H., Ugbolue, U.C., Sorbie, G.G., Lam, W.K., Grace, F.M., Iacono, A.D., Liang, M., Dutheil, F., Gu, Y. and Baker, J.S., 2022.

Conference Presentations

- a) Reliability of Forearm Muscle Electromyography Data During Multi-Planar Maximum Voluntary Contraction Grip and Wrist Articulation. Hunter, H., Sorbie, G., Grace, F., Gu, Y., Baker, J. S. and Ugbolue, U. C., Oct 2016, Proceedings of the Sixth Asian Society of Sport Biomechanics Conference (ASSB 2016): Asian Sport Biomechanics Research Trend, Ningbo, China, October. 13-16, 2016. Li, J. and Gu, Y. (eds.). IACSIT Press, p. 115-115 1 p. IR39

- b) An Evaluation of Club Angle Parameters During Golf Swings Using Low Cost Video Analyses Packages. Hunter, H., Sorbie, G., Grace, F., Gu, Y., Baker, J. S. and Ugbolue, U. C., Oct 2016, Proceedings of the Sixth Asian Society of Sport Biomechanics Conference (ASSB 2016): Asian Sport Biomechanics Research Trend, Ningbo, China, October. 13-16, 2016. Li, J. and Gu, Y. (eds.). IACSIT Press, p. 191-191 1 p. TC66

- c) Do Hand Grip Sizes Influence Forearm Muscle Activity and Golf Performance During Golf Swings? Sorbie, G., Hunter, H., Grace, F., Gu, Y., Baker, J. S. and Ugbolue, U. C., 2016, Proceedings of the Sixth Asian Society of Sport Biomechanics Conference (ASSB 2016): Asian Sport Biomechanics Research Trend, Ningbo, China, October 13-16, 2016. Li, J. and Gu, Y. (eds.). IACSIT Press, p. 192-192 1 p. TC67

Conference Abstract Publications

Effect of Fatigue on Hip, Knee and Ankle Proprioception During a Golf Specific Fatigue Protocol. Hunter, H.H., Sorbie, G.G., Grace, F.M., Dello Iacono, A., Baker, J.S. and Ugbole, U.C. 2021, Paper presented at XXVIII Congress of the International Society of Biomechanics, 25/07/21 - 29/07/21.

Statement of Originality

The work in this thesis is the sole work of the candidate. This work has not been previously submitted for award at any other institution. To the best of my knowledge, this thesis contains no material that has been previously published by another person except where due reference is made in the thesis itself.

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26/08/2022...

Henry Hunter

Date

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Biomechanics in golf allows the golfer to improve technique and performance by applying the fundamental principles of mechanics (Hume et al., 2005). Biomechanical analysis and intervention are frequently used to improve the technique and performance of the golfer by applying proven mechanisms and principles (Hume et al., 2005). These principles associated with the golf swing are stability, Newton's laws of motion (inertia, acceleration, and action reaction), lever arms and the stretch-shorten cycle (Hume et al., 2005). A number of sports science disciplines have been used to improve golf performance and reduce injury. Biomechanics has been used in an attempt to find the model golf swing for the individual golfer (Hume et al., 2005). There are generally three main areas within golf biomechanics that are utilised during assessment. These are: electromyography, kinematics and kinetics.

Electromyography (EMG) is a technique used to evaluate muscle activities by detecting electrical potential signals generated by muscle cells. It is widely used in the areas of medical research, rehabilitation, ergonomics and also sports science (Rashid et al., 2015). This study will focus on the muscle activity of specific golf related muscles during the golf swing. This electrical activity from motor units can be recorded from a muscle with both non-invasive surface electromyography (sEMG) and invasive (intramuscular EMG) electrodes (Farina and Negro, 2012). Surface electromyography is used extensively as a biomechanics analysis tool within golf scientific research due to its non-invasive capacity to measure muscle action potentials and the output of quantitative data on the activity during dynamic muscle contractions (Tortora and Derrickson, 2011).

SEMG has previously been used to evaluate muscle fatigue during the golf swing (Horton et al., 2001) as well as analysing the activation levels of various muscles including the forearm (Farber et al., 2009), (Glazebrook et al., 1994). High levels of forearm muscle activation during the golf swing can be closely related to wrist and elbow injuries (Farber et al., 2009).

Kinematics of the golf swing is an area that has been extensively researched and focuses on the movement of the body (or parts of the body) during the golf swing. This research includes comparisons of the kinematic outputs whilst using different clubs (Egret, 2003), how to maximise distance and accuracy of the golf shot, (Hume et al., 2005), as well as reducing golf injury rate and kinematic changes between professional and amateur golfers (Zheng et al., 2007). The golf swing itself is a specific movement that comprises of an intricate series of events that culminate at the point of impact to maximise the performance variable of an effective golf swing (Cole and Grimshaw, 2015). The golf swing generates a large amount of force and can be considered to be accountable for a large majority of reported golf-related injuries (Gosheger et al., 2003), (Marta et al., 2012). These injuries tend to originate either from: poor swing mechanics, a traumatic cause (for example hitting a tree root with the clubhead during a swing), poor physical conditioning or the overuse of muscles (Cabri et al., 2009), (Thériault and Lachance, 1998).

Kinetics are used to evaluate the forces generated during the golf swing. Previous investigations include examining the weight transfer of the body during the golf swing between different skilled golfers (Okuda et al., 2010), as well as the centre of pressure patterns during the golf swing (Ball and Best, 2012).

Strength and conditioning has also been used to improve the physical characteristics of the golfer and improve the golf swing through physical training programmes (Hume et al., 2005), (Jenkins, 2007), (Thomas et al., 2010), (Smith et al., 2012).

In addition, psychological techniques have been investigated to enable the golfer to perform better under pressure (An et al., 2013) and physics strengthened with applied biomechanics and design technology have been used to improve golf equipment (Milne and Davis, 1992) .

A larger, overarching study has been performed by the biomechanical research group within the School of Science and Sport, Institute for Clinical Exercise & Health Science, University of the West of Scotland, UK. This encompasses a number of studies by different authors to create and validate specific golf related protocols. It will also investigate the suitability of the institute's biomechanical facilities within a golf environment which may help improve performance or decrease the chance of injury.

All studies have utilised either the Myon 320 EMG system, various 2D motion capture software systems, the Vicon Bonita motion analysis system or a combination of each of these technologies. Current published papers from this overall study include:

Reliability of Forearm Muscle Electromyography Data During Multi-Planar Maximum Voluntary Contraction Grip and Wrist Articulation, (Hunter et al., 2016). This study used the Myon system and a custom rig to ensure that participants remain in the same position throughout the trials. Signals from the ECRB and FDS muscles were utilised.

Intra-session and Inter-day Reliability of the Myon 320 Electromyography System during Sub-maximal Contractions, (Sorbie et al., 2018). Utilised the above EMG system and rig with the addition of a 10 kg Taishan bumper plate weight. Different tests were performed on the ECRB, anterior deltoid and the vastus lateralis.

An Electromyographic Study of the Effect of Hand Grip Sizes on Forearm Muscle Activity and Golf Performance, (Sorbie et al., 2016). Used the Myon system to measure both the ECRB and FDS in both the validated rig then during a fifteen-golf swing trial (with three different grip sizes on the clubs).

Commercial Golf Glove Effects on Golf Performance and Forearm Muscle Activity, (Sorbie, et al., 2017). Participants were analysed during a trial of 32 golf swings. During this time the EMG output of the ECRB and FDS as well as the participant/club positions were measured by the Myon system and the Vicon Bonita system.

Electromyography Analysis of the Erector Spinae Muscle During the Golf Swing when Using Four Different Golf Clubs, (Sorbie et al., 2017b). Again, used the Myon system to measure EMG signals from the erector spinae muscle during a 25-shot golf trial. The Vicon system was again utilised to synchronise the EMG system with the five phases of the golf swing.

Comparison of Thoracic and Lumbar Erector Spinae Muscle Activation Before and After a Golf Practice Session, (Sorbie et al., 2017a). Used both Myon and Vicon Bonita systems to collect the data for this trial both before and after a specific (125 golf shot) fatigue protocol with a 7-iron golf club.

Effect of Fatigue on Hip, Knee and Ankle Proprioception During a Golf Specific Fatigue Protocol, (Hunter et al., 2021). Used the same golf fatigue protocol as above (with only the Vicon Bonita system) to measure hip, knee and ankle angle differences in a pre and post fatigue state.

An Evaluation of Temporal and Club Angle Parameters During Golf Swings Using Low-Cost Video Analyses Packages, (Hunter et al., 2022). This study utilised the Vicon Bonita system to compare the golf club angle parameters during six golf swing phases against three low cost, augmented video-based portable systems (AVPS).

Analysis of the X-Factor and X-Factor Stretch During the Completion of a Golf Practice Session in Low-Handicap Golfers, (Sorbie et al., 2018). This study also used the previously mentioned golf fatigue protocol with the Vicon Bonita system to compare the X-Factor and X-Factor stretch in a pre and post golf practice session.

1.2. Outline of Each Chapter Within the Thesis

1.2.1. Chapter 2 Literature Review

This chapter contains a literature review that will set the background of the research within the sport of golf and examines the rationale of why a different data capture system would be advantageous to performance and injury prevention. This is followed by a review of EMG and kinematics literature. This section examines the history of kinematics as a whole and closely investigates different uses of this science before further examining the current usage and potential future usages within a golf environment.

1.2.2. Chapter 3 Study 1

Reliability of Forearm Muscle Electromyography Data During Multi-Planar Maximum Voluntary Contraction Grip and Wrist Articulation. The purpose of this study is to measure, collect and analyse the electrical muscle signal output during five trials and determine the impact on hand morphology. This study focused mainly on the flexor digitorum superficialis and the extensor carpi radialis brevis.

1.2.3. Chapter 4 Study 2

2D Motion, An Evaluation of Temporal and Club Angle Parameters During Golf Swings Using Low-Cost Video Analyses Packages. The purpose of this study is to validate a 2D augmented video-based portable system (AVPS) against a gold standard 3D motion analysis system (Vicon motion systems Ltd. Oxford, UK) which has been designed to evaluate human movement within a clinical and sport setting using low-cost software packages. Multiple low-cost augmented video-based portable systems were utilised and both kinematic and temporal parameters were compared against the gold standard 3D Vicon motion analysis system.

This study aims to address the following:

- To validate Siliconcoach Pro 7 software against the 3D Vicon motion analysis system during golf swings.
- To validate Siliconcoach Live software against the 3D Vicon motion analysis system during golf swings.
- To validate Kinovea software against the 3D Vicon motion analysis system during golf swings.

1.2.4. Chapter 5 Study 3

Effect of Fatigue on Hip, Knee and Ankle Proprioception During a Golf Specific Fatigue Protocol. The purpose of this study is to use the gold standard Vicon system to investigate the changes in kinematic variables of the lower limbs before and after fatigue. The study also compared the effects of fatigue across different clubs and the effects on the hip, knee and ankle.

1.2.5. Chapter 6 Overall Discussion

This final chapter will form the general discussion of the thesis. It shall discuss each area of the thesis (purposes, aims, research questions, main findings, overview of limitations, recommendations for future research) and will finally provide a conclusion to the thesis.

2. Review of Literature

2.1. Theory of Kinematics

Kinematics is the study of human movement that identifies the position and orientation of a segment (POSE). This is relative to other segments with the consideration of time to quantify this movement without referencing the forces that are produced to allow movement (Cappozzo et al., 2005), (Cereatti et al., 2017), (Colyer et al., 2018). Biomechanically, human movement can be described as an interacting system of rigid bodies (Lu and O'Connor, 1999). Because of this interaction, reliably capturing the kinematic measurements of normal lower limb movement prove to be challenging.

There has been a number of studies that highlight the importance of human motion analysis, to help screen and identify biomechanical impairments of the lower limbs (King et al., 2018), (Bagwell et al., 2015), (Hewett and Bates, 2017), (Kotsifaki et al., 2020), (Silva et al., 2014) or abnormal motion control (Dai et al., 2012), (Willy and Davis, 2011). It is still unclear whether better injury prevention can be achieved by improved movement competency. Bisi et al. (2017) define movement competency as “the development of sufficient skill to assure successful performance in different physical activities”. However, additional biomechanical profiling may assist in the increase of physical improvement (Slauterbeck et al., 2019), (McCall et al., 2017).

2.2. Biomechanics of the Golf Swing

The “perfect” swing is every golfer’s ultimate goal. Every time the ball is addressed, a combination of factors can have an impact on the flight of the ball and the outcome of the shot. From this point, the forces within the golf swing should be structured to ensure the club head should arrive back at the same point prior to impact at the correct velocity, position, direction, angle of attack (the vertical direction of the club head’s geometric center movement at maximum compression of the golf ball) and orientation to ensure the correct flight path of the ball is achieved. A study by Hume et al. (2005) points out that coaches look for consistent and mechanically sound movements with their participant’s swings, but many previous investigations focus on the increase in shot distance (primarily with the driver).

Suttie (2006) describes this as a consistent swing that will deliver the clubface to the ball at the point of impact, in a square alignment to the target line at maximal velocity and the clubface being perfectly vertical. These skilled actions are described by (Bril et al., 2010) that comprise a combination of flexibility, precision, adaptability, smoothness, regularity, optimisation and swiftness.

Hume et al. (2005) explain that “golf biomechanics applies the principles and technique of mechanics to the structure and function of the golfer in an effort to improve golf technique and performance”. Specifically, golf biomechanics examines the joint forces, muscle activity patterns as well as movement characteristics of the swing therefore, a better understanding of optimal swing mechanics would be better when analysing an elite player’s swing (McCarroll et al., 2016).

According to Maddalozzo (1987) the ball should be positioned at the lowest point of the full swing, left of the target line center and towards the left inside heel (right-handed players). When addressing the ball, both posture and alignment can directly affect the swing plane, club head pathway as well as the transfer of weight and balance during the swing (Kirby et al., 1985).

Newell and Corocos (1993) have suggested that variability of movement can regularly be viewed as noise (disturbance) within the central nervous system and should be classified as dysfunctional. Williams and Davids (2005) note that the movement variability is intrinsic within a skilled motor performance and allows the performers adaption and flexibility in their environment. Within a golf environment, Langdown et al. (2012) describes movement variability as the changes in swing kinematics and kinetics from trial to trial when the golfer attempts to hit the same shot. These changes will emerge due to constraints of the golfer's body, the environment and the task. Many studies have investigated methods of increasing power, distance and accuracy of a golf swing. Fradkin et al. (2004) have shown that a golfer’s performance will be significantly improved by undertaking a golf specific warm up, Tuxen (2009) describes four biomechanical points that can impact the flight of a golf ball as well as Vengellow and Santiago (2008) who established the correct clubs for different golfing populations.

2.3. Golf Background

Golf is recognised as a low-risk activity in comparison to other sports with higher injury rates such as football and basketball and is deemed to be a non-strenuous activity because of the marginal aerobic effort required (Stockard, 2001), (Batt, 1992).

Cabri et al. (2009) has reviewed the literature of golf related musculoskeletal injuries (Figure 2.1) which points out that injuries usually originate from traumatic causes or overuse. Research by McHardy et al. (2007) shows a 15.8% injury incident rate with the lower back being most prominent at (18.3%), closely followed by elbow/forearm (17.2%), foot/ankle (12.9%) and shoulder/upper arm (11.8%). Other studies have also researched that general golfing injuries are usually in the neck, shoulders, wrist, hands and knees. They also note that the lower back is the most common golf injury, this may be due to the dynamic nature of the golf swing (McHardy et al., 2007).

Figure 2.1: Possible Locations of Golfing Injuries, Cabri et al. (2009)

Kao et al. (1995) found that there is a significant difference in activity between the trailing and leading arms during the golf swing and emphasises the importance of the scapular muscle during this time.

A study by Farber et al. (2009) shows that professional and amateur golfers display differing levels of muscle activity in the pronator teres during the golf swing. The flexor carpi radialis (FCR) and pronator teres (PT) muscles are thought to be most affected in medial epicondylitis, whereas the extensor carpi radialis brevis (ECRB) muscle is thought to be most affected in lateral epicondylitis.

The flexor carpi ulnaris (FCU) muscle has been shown to provide the greatest stabilising force against valgus torque at the elbow and has an anatomical advantage as it lies directly over the medial collateral ligament. Previous studies have suggested that lateral epicondylitis is more common in the lead arm (left arm in a right-handed golfer), whereas medial epicondylitis is more common in the trail arm (right arm in a right-handed golfer) (Farber et al., 2009), (Zouzias *et al.*, 2018). Research by Glazebrook et al. (1994) found that the mean flexor muscle electromyographic activity of participants with medial epicondylitis was significantly greater than that of asymptomatic participants in both address and swing phases. The authors concluded that excessive activity of the wrist flexors during the address and backswing phases, combined with a burst of flexor activity, during wrist extension prior to impact, may be a causative factor for medial epicondylitis. They also note that there was no significant difference between symptomatic and asymptomatic participants when a forearm brace and oversized grip was imposed.

Hand and wrist golfing injuries tend to occur on impact and usually damages either bone, nerve or soft tissue (Hutson and Speed, 2011). A poor swing technique, tight grip or too much practice may also contribute to injury (Meira and Brumitt, 2010). Equally, clubs with old or substandard grips can also increase injury risks, (Theriault et al., 1998). Any heavy sudden contact (striking a tree root) could also cause injury (Gosheger et al., 2003).

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Long term injuries such as tendinitis or arthritis in the hand and wrist can occur when pain in these areas has been ignored for some time. According to Parziale and Mallon (2006) and Hume et al. (2005), a reduction of pressure of the golf grip will help relieve or reduce pain.

2.4. Golf Related Injuries of the Hip, Knee and Ankle

A study by Bechler et al. (1995) has investigated the hip and knee muscle signals of both legs in elite and non-elite golfers during their golf swing. The study showed no significant difference between the two groups. Although great force is shown in both the leading and trailing legs of a golfer, injuries of the lower limb are significantly less common than upper limb and back (Gatt et al., 1998). Similarly, hip injuries are uncommon even though high degrees of rotation occur during the golf swing. Some reports of trochanteric bursitis have been observed, mostly by women which may be caused by walking on the uneven surfaces of a golf course (McCarroll et al., 2016).

There are many studies that are inconclusive with regards to knee, ankle and foot injuries and their frequency. Baker (2007) highlights a lack of consensus in literature regarding knee loading and the risk of injury during a golf swing and Marshall and McNair (2013) point out that there is little data available on the ability of participants to generate internal rotation torque in the lower limb with a magnitude that may cause tissue failure. Gatt et al. (1998) however, points out that high torsional and compressive forces are seen in the hip, knee and ankles during golf swings. Suckel and Best (2006) observed that golfers with a knee or hip joint endo-prosthesis are able to maintain or even improve their current handicap after surgery.

Lynn and Noffal (2010) point out that during the golf swing, a large valgus moment on the target side knee does not decrease with external rotation of the foot at address.

Krosshaug et al. (2007) and Dix et al. (2019) describe this dynamic valgus as a combination of hip adduction and internal rotation, knee abduction and internal rotation of the tibia. The activation of the hip extensors, abductors and external rotator muscles is thought to control frontal or transverse plane movement (Grimaldi et al., 2015), (Ford et al., 2015), (Neamatallah et al., 2020) however, evidence from literature in this area is inconclusive. Cronström et al. (2020) show that future studies are warranted in the investigation of ACL injury during knee abduction. Dix et al. (2019) demonstrates that there is conflicting evidence for a relationship between hip muscle strength and lower extremity dynamic valgus in female athletes. Cronström et al. (2016) highlights a gap in the research on factors associated with knee abduction in men and in patients with knee injuries.

2.5. Injury Prevention

Studies show that to allow more flow and movement during the golf swing, players should apply a lighter grip by repositioning the left hand counterclockwise. Hume et al. (2005) observed that this lighter grip gave better control of the club face and improved movement of the hands and wrists. Geisler (2001) found that golfers with a radial deviation of lower than 10 degrees realised that a left-hand grip was more comfortable. However, a neutral grip was more suitable where radial deviation was found to be more than 15 degrees. Golf clubs can be adjusted to a golfer's needs. Shaft stiffness, shaft length and differences in grip are all variables that may assist injury prevention. As mentioned above, golf grip can be crucial to prevent wrist, forearm and elbow pain generated through excess tension.

Handgrip strength testing is a method that has been extensively used in various sporting settings. It can be used in a range of clinical settings, especially in hand therapy (Fess, 1986) because it is fast, simple, reliable and delivers the ability to

provide simple analysis (Fess, 1986). Grip and pinch strength are the two most common ways to assess hand function and strength (Nissenkorn and Ben-Zeev, 2012). Handgrip strength is one of the most reliable and practical ways to measure human strength which has been highlighted in research by Innes (1999).

It is commonly used as an indication of strength in adults (Newman et al., 1984). Studies by Neamatallah et al. (2020) and Granacher et al. (2016) also note that movement deficiencies and risk of injury may be associated with lower strength levels.

Countless everyday tasks and sporting skills depend on high activity levels of the forearm flexor muscles. The flexor musculature of the forearms and hands are responsible for grip strength which may help in the prevention of injury as well as an indicator of an athletes' overall strength. Grip strength may also play a role in injury prevention and rehabilitation. In many cases, rehabilitation for injuries such as tennis elbow includes strengthening of the hand grip. According to Poliquin (2006), "these ailments are often caused by improper strength ratios between the elbow muscles and the forearm muscles. If the elbow flexors, like the biceps and brachialis, are too strong for the forearm flexors, uneven tension accumulates in the soft tissue and results in elbow pain".

2.6. Electromyography

Electromyography (EMG) is a technique that can be used for monitoring myoelectric activity during muscular contractions (De Luca, 1997), (Cifrek et al., 2009). It can also be used to assess muscle activity during both isometric and dynamic contractions (Masuda et al., 1999), (Yang and Winter, 1983). The electrical activity of motor units can be recorded from a muscle with both non-invasive (surface electromyography (sEMG)) and invasive (intramuscular EMG) electrodes (Farina

and Negro, 2012). These techniques have been used in both clinical settings (Hamilton-Wright, 2005) as well as performance analysis (Adelsberg, 1986), (Ekstrom et al., 2007).

There have been a number of handgrip related studies published that examine forearm muscle activity and mainly focus on the flexor muscles which include: the flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS) (Hägg and Milerad, 1997), (Oskouei et al., 2013), (Hoozemans and Van Dieën, 2005), (Kong and Lowe, 2005), the flexor carpi radialis (FCR) (Duque et al., 1995), (Ekenstam et al., 2009), (De Monsabert et al., 2012), (Hoozemans and Van Dieën, 2005) and extensor muscles to include: the extensor carpi radialis brevis (ECRB) (Ekenstam et al., 2009), (De Monsabert et al., 2012), (Hägg and Milerad, 1997), (Hoozemans and Van Dieën, 2005) and the extensor carpi ulnaris (ECU) (Ekenstam et al., 2009), (Hoozemans and Van Dieën, 2005).

2.7. Use of Electromyography in Sport

Studies have investigated sport related EMG signals to analyse initiation as well as activation levels of muscles during athletic type actions. It has also been used during repeated actions to measure fatigue within the muscle tissue (Caldwell et al., 2003), (Hautier et al., 2000), (Horton et al., 2001), (Adelsberg, 1986), (De Jesus et al., 2015), (Farber et al., 2009), (Hatch et al., 2006), (Marta et al., 2015). Because of the individual nature of EMG, it is not surprising that its suitability within a team sport environment is minimal (Clarys and Cabri, 1993).

Many studies have been carried out on individual sports. These include studies by Chapman et al. (2010), who compared surface EMG in cycling using fine needle EMG. Hautier et al. (2000) measured EMG and force during a specific leg muscle fatigue trial and Jobson et al. (2013) who compared inter and intra session reliability of leg muscle activity of both cyclists and non-cyclists.

Rowing studies were carried out by Caldwell et al. (2003) who investigated the changes in lumbar flexion together with the pattern and level of muscle activity of selected erector spinae during a rowing trial. Turpin et al. (2011) quantified the effect of fatigue on muscle coordination during a constant load cyclic rowing exercise on multiple muscles.

Tennis studies were carried out by Adelsberg (1986) who analysed the effect that different racket grip sizes have on the muscle activity of the forearm and shoulder. Hatch et al. (2006) used fine-wire electromyography to measure muscle activity in the extensor carpi radialis longus and brevis, extensor digitorum communis, flexor carpi radialis and pronator teres and compared results with three different handgrip sizes.

Swimming studies by Caty et al. (2007) evaluated the stabilisation of the wrist joint and ad hoc wrist muscles activations during the two principal phases of the freestyle stroke. De Jesus et al. (2015) compared EMG activity of both arm and leg muscles during a backstroke start. Also Olstad et al. (2016) analysed muscular activation patterns and kinematic variables during the complete stroke cycle (SC) and the different phases of breaststroke, swimming at both submaximal and maximal efforts.

Within golf, Cole and Grimshaw (2015) reviewed literature that investigated the biomechanics of the modern golf swing, the EMG variable outputs throughout the phases of a swing as well as golf related lower back injuries.

Farber et al. (2009) examined the difference in EMG output of the flexor carpi radialis, pronator teres, flexor carpi ulnaris and extensor carpi radialis brevis muscles of both forearms between professional and amateur golfers.

Glazebrook et al. (1994) compared EMG output of the flexor and extensor muscles on golfers with and without medial epicondylitis. Marta et al. (2015) described and compared EMG patterns of lower limb muscles throughout the golf swing with three

different clubs. These previously mentioned studies show that whilst EMG has been used for a variety of uses across multiple sports, many of these uses and their containing variables can be used within an individual golfing context.

2.8. Use of Electromyography in Golf

A number of golf related studies have used EMG to analyse muscle activity during the golf swing. McHardy and Pollard (2005) and Marta et al. (2012) have noted that EMG studies can provide an explanation of why certain trunk, upper and lower body muscles are active during the specific phases of the golf swing in relation to the movement of the body during the swing.

Other studies have investigated muscle activation levels within identified areas of interest. These studies provided an insight into how muscle activity levels may affect injury mechanisms and the performance of the golfer.

Horton et al. (2001), investigated abdominal muscle activation of elite golfers with and without chronic lower back pain. This study found that although repetitive golf swings did increase pain in those with chronic lower back pain, it could not conclude whether abdominal muscle activity was the cause or effect. Studies by Marta et al. (2013) and Marta et al. (2015) investigated the use of multiple golf clubs and their effect on trunk and lower limb muscles. Findings included higher activation of the trunk rotators, right hamstrings and semitendinosus.

Bechler et al. (1995) examined electrical muscle activity in seven hip and knee muscles of the lead (left) and trail (right) legs of competitive golfers during a golf swing. Findings not only revealed that the trail hip extensors and abductors as well as the lead adductor magus initiated pelvic rotation during forward swing, but also that the peak EMG muscle activity recorded in the hips and knees occurred in an earlier phase than that measured previously in the trunk and shoulder.

This confirmed the sequential firing pattern of the hip and knee muscles that takes place during the competitive golf swing. Watkins et al. (1996) demonstrated the importance of trunk muscles in stabilising and controlling the loading response for maximal power and accuracy in the golfer's swing. These studies have investigated various muscles including the lower extremity (Table 2.1) during the golf swing.

Table 2.1: *Lower Extremity Muscles Examined*

Study	Muscles Examined
(Bechler et al., 1995)	UGM, LGM, GMED, ADM, BF, ST, VL
(Watkins et al., 1996)	GM
(Marta et al., 2013)	GM
(Marta et al., 2016)	TA, PL, GM, GL, BF,ST, GM, VM, RF, VL

UGM – Upper Gluteus Maximus; LGM – Lower Gluteus Maximus; GMED – Gluteus Medius; TA – Tibialis Anterior; PL – Peroneus Longus; GM – Gastrocnemius Medialis; GL – Gastrocnemius Lateralis, BF – Biceps Femoris, ST – Semitendinosus, GM – Gluteus Maximus, VM – Vastus Medialis, RF – Rectus Femoris; VL – Vastus Lateralis.

2.9. Forearm Muscle Activity During the Golf Swing

Farber et al. (2009) and Glazebrook et al. (1994) have investigated forearm muscle activity during the golf swing where Farber et al. (2009) also investigated the difference in forearm muscle activity between professional and amateur golfers. These studies have shown that in some phases of the golf swing, amateurs produced a higher muscle output than that of professionals. They have also found that previous medial epicondylitis led to a higher muscle activity in the forearm.

2.10. 2D/3D Video Analysis

2-Dimensional biomechanical analysis can be traced back to the late nineteenth century and the pioneering work of Eadweard Muybridge, who first developed techniques to capture image sequences of equine gait (Muybridge, 1887). Studies by Schurr et al. (2017) and Herrington (2017) have shown that whilst 2D video analysis systems are shown to be reliable, they do not reflect the difficulty in achieving this reliability during the complex manual image processing methods.

Many studies that use 2D visual/video assessment to validate lower limb movement have not used a validated gold standard 3D biomechanical analysis system. Norris and Olsen (2011) compared intrarater, interrater and test-reliability of 2D video analysis of sagittal plane angles at the hip and knee during mechanical lifting. Welling et al. (2018) investigated single leg hop test after ACL reconstruction using 2D cameras. Markerless motion capture (systems without anatomical markers on parts of the body) are not reliant on biomechanical expertise, time or expensive lab-based set up (Colyer et al., 2018). The use of 2D systems can be advantageous when monitoring neuromuscular interventions or athletic movement. This technology, if considered to be accurate and reliable (kinematic variables ($P \leq 0.05$), (Ugbolue et al., 2013)) and could assist with the assessment of movement quality, fluency and efficiency.

2.10.1. Marker-Based System Considerations

Marker-based motion capture systems are considered the gold standard of kinematic motion analysis. These systems rely on accurate placings of motion markers on anatomical landmarks around the human body. These points have been quantified in early cadaveric studies by Dempster (1956) and defined human body segment lengths, center of mass and segment volume (Clauser et al., 1969).

Two such systems are Qualisys (ProReflex, Qualisys Inc., Sweden) and Vicon (Oxford Metrics, U.K.). These are both optoelectronic systems that have multiple infrared cameras and passive reflective markers to define segments (Van Der Kruk and Reijne, 2018). Passive (usually retro reflective) markers are visible to the camera to track the 3D marker trajectory. The systems then collect this trajectory and interacts with the global coordinate system (GCS).

The paths of the markers are captured by multiple cameras in order to define the movement of the markers in a 3D space. A single camera can only establish motion in two dimensions; therefore, a three-dimensional system will require a minimum of two cameras at different locations to complete a 3D image (Mauntel et al., 2017). Software uses calibration data to form the 2D positional data for each camera and then calculate the 3D coordinates and changes in the coordinate position, this gives motion quantification within the captured volume (Di Marco et al., 2017).

Marker-based systems have been used to evaluate gait and human movement analysis in both normative and clinical populations (Leboeuf et al., 2019), (Wen et al., 2018), (Bagwell et al., 2015) as a baseline of motion in both pre and post therapeutic intervention (Hewett et al., 2005), (Nagelli et al., 2019), (King et al., 2018), (Gore et al., 2020) and post-surgical intervention (Wren et al., 2011), (Lamontagne et al., 2009), (Brown-Taylor et al., 2020), (Nagelli et al., 2019).

As previously mentioned, the use of 3D marker-based systems has many overheads, this includes extensive biomechanical expertise, significant post-processing time and clinical accessibility (Colyer et al., 2018). It has also been noted that some athletes claimed restricted movement was caused by marker placement (van der Kruk and Reijne, 2018). However, there is a shortage of literature to support this claim.

2.10.2. Low-Cost Augmented Video Based Portable Systems

As previously mentioned, an alternative method to analyse movement is through 2D video capture and analysis. This has already been identified as a method of assessing GAIT from 2D motion systems (AVPS) and software to the gold standard 3D motion analysis packages by Vicon (Hunter et al., 2022), (Sorbie et al., 2017b) (Ugbolue et al., 2013). There are numerous systems that can be used in the 2D analysis comparison and motion analysis. These systems may also be more intuitive for less experienced users and may display the same outcomes as the gold standard 3D Vicon systems. This may benefit smaller clinics and allow for faster rehabilitation (Fatone and Stine, 2015).

2.10.3. System Comparison

Previous research on Gait analysis, has shown that both AVPS and 3D systems are both reliable and can replicate results in the given field of investigation. It unfortunately also states that the use of the AVPS has only been tested when the motion occurs and when a participant is directly in front of the camera (Ugbolue et al., 2013). This may cause difficulties when more technical movements are to be implemented as any variance may not occur in the correct plane (Chu et al., 2010).

There is a recurring area of importance throughout the literature which points out that the need for rehabilitation clinics is increasing (Alkan et al., 2013). Due to the gold standard Vicon system being expensive it creates high demand for this specialist motion analysis treatment as part of the rehabilitation process. Prior research has identified that the AVPS is accurate to a point but may present issues in rehabilitation when in direct comparison with the gold standard systems. The AVPS can analyse golf swings and identify possible cause of injury for example McHardy et al. (2006) note that injuries can be related to badly executed golf swings, especially

at ball impact. Although the golf swing is not an intensive or exhausting movement, it still stresses the skeletal-muscle systems which can be related to injuries such as back pain (Cabri et al., 2009) and (Gluck et al., 2008), that can be related to the mechanical movement of the swing (Lim et al., 2012).

Ugbolue et al. (2013) states that previous research indicates the use of high cost, high maintenance 3D motion systems are for clinical use and clinical rehabilitation as well as use by physiotherapists. These 3D systems cannot be easily afforded by clinical and sports rehabilitation centres. Some AVPS systems have been considered acceptable for use in clinical settings and will produce similar results to that of the Vicon system. This may allow smaller clinics to use the AVPS as a viable alternative to the more expensive system, allowing for cheaper rehabilitation costs with similar experience. This research plans to validate a small selection of 2D motion analysis systems against 3D motion analysis systems in a golf swing environment. The results of this study will be explained and suggestions for further research will be made. This will also act as a validation protocol for further research studies.

As previously discussed, motion analysis can be utilised in many various sporting contexts, especially where the method of analysis focuses on fault identification and improvement. Golf is a good example of a sport that can benefit from more detailed biomechanical underpinning of the golf swing technical movements. It has been highlighted by golf coaching professionals that the most important aspect for optimum driving performance (increased ball velocity) is the mechanics of a golf swing. Thus, making driving performance a key aspect to focus on for the majority of golfers, both amateur and professional (Chu et al., 2010).

2.10.4. 3D Motion Analysis Systems

Cimolin and Galli (2014) state that 3D gait analysis is a powerful tool in clinical practices for scientific purpose as it provides comprehensive data on normal and pathological gait and objective analysis in kinetics, kinematics, spatio-temporal data, and joint moments. However, it was also stated in the study that 3D analysis produced vast amounts of data. 3D analysis is complex to use, and it can be difficult and time consuming to collate and interpret all of the data provided. It has also been noted that for a patient's results to be reliable, a lot of training is required beforehand. Therefore, for these reasons, a small clinic may not have the time, skill or space for the equipment required to perform 3D analysis. It has been suggested that within clinical practice, 3D gait laboratory equipment is scarcely seen and these tend to be more university or specialised research hospital based (Carse et al., 2013).

Carse et al. (2013) highlight that the Vicon MX system is old and widely used. The results of this study showed to be highly accurate and showed less variable output in comparison to another 3D motion system (Optitrack).

Previous studies of golf using 3D motion capture include: Chu et al. (2010) who researched the golf swing of a wide variety group of golfers using the Peak Motus System, now known as Vicon. This study looked at five golf swing phases: address, top of back swing, acceleration, impact and follow through. Results showed a 44% to 74% variance in ball velocity. Pantzar-Castilla et al. (2018) compared the knee joint sagittal plane movement output of 2D markerless and 3D gait analysis systems in participants with cerebral palsy. The study finds an overestimation of the 2D values of knee flexion/extension angles by 3% to 7% compared to the 3D system. Overall, the reliability within 2D and 3D was classed as mostly good to excellent.

2.10.5. 2D Motion Analysis Systems

As previously mentioned, a cheaper alternative to the 3D motion analysis system is the (2D) low-cost augmented video-based portable system (AVPS) (Ugbolue et al., 2013). The computer/software based 2D systems that have been used within this thesis are Siliconcoach Pro, Siliconcoach Live and Kinovea. A study on ten male participants, age ($22.7\text{yr} \pm 3.6$) conducted by Cronin et al. (2006) concluded that Siliconcoach was beneficial in the determination of the end range of static and dynamic motion, thus this may be a functional and cost-effective aspect within a clinical environment. Siliconcoach Live is one of the first comprehensive online video analysis system which encapsulates analysis and feedback in an online environment. To date, there is little research, which compares the accuracy of Siliconcoach Pro or Live. Similarly, Kinovea is also a low cost (free) 2D video analysis environment. As it is free and open source, it is therefore more appealing and affordable for clinical practices. There have been various sporting studies carried out that have used Kinovea to analyse biomechanical movement.

A gait analysis study by Fernández-González et al. (2020) displayed good intraclass correlation for the hip, knee and ankles whilst comparing Kinovea software against the gold standard Vicon 3D motion system. Balsalobre-Fernández et al. (2013) measured flight time of vertical jumps and found that this low-cost method provided reliable and valid measurements. Kinovea, has also not currently been tested for reliability for both, gait or golf swing analysis.

Clinicians may also find that these various 2D systems require significantly less training and produce much less data than their 3D counterparts. This may also lead to a decrease in time spent assessing the severity of injuries or monitoring patient progress (Baker, 2007).

2.10.6. Comparison of the 2D and 3D Motion Systems

It is essential to validate various 2D motion analysis systems and find a suitable comparison with 3D motion analysis systems, since they are known to be complex and expensive, as the need for rehabilitation within clinical settings is an issue that is rising (Alkan et al., 2013). Quantitative numerical data can be captured and analysed using data collected from golf club swing trials. Comparison between 2D and 3D systems can be analysed to determine the reliability of the 2D system. Validity may be measured by comparing the results of the 2D systems against the 3D gold standard (Vicon).

2.11. Muscular Fatigue During the Golf Swing

Fatigue is defined by Fitts (1994) as a failure to maintain the required or expected force output or failing to maintain the required or expected power output. According to studies by Lucci et al. (2011) and Miller and Bird (1976), hip and knee mechanics can be substantially altered whilst fatigued. However, Higdon et al. (2012) points out that both “golf specific fatigue did not relate to the initial lower body sagittal plane angles at address nor was simulated golf specific fatigue related to peak transverse plane pelvis and trunk rotational velocities (or their timings) in a manner that indicates a relationship to resultant club head velocity (CHV) and shot consistency”. Laboratory studies have shown that the neuromuscular control of the lower limb is compromised in the fatigued state (Hiemstra et al., 2001). George and Robinson (2010) found that fatigue does appear to affect some lower-limb biomechanics during single-limb landings. Johnston et al. (1998) found that participants had a significantly decreased ability to maintain balance on one or both legs after fatiguing the lower limbs to less than 50% of original strength values.

Wojtys et al. (1996) found that a fatiguing protocol on a dynamometer delayed voluntary muscle reaction time, decreased firing rates of the hamstrings and quadriceps as well as delaying spinal reflexes. Studies by Carpenter et al. (2016), Pedersen et al. (1999), McCloskey (1973), and Taimela et al. (1999) have also shown similar effects in the shoulder, elbow and lumbar spine. Salavati et al. (2007) have found that fatigue of the proximal lower extremity muscles can affect postural stability and fatigue of the frontal movers and can be associated with postural instability in the frontal plane. Miller and Bird (1976) consider the knee and hip flexors/extensors are the most important muscle group for performance on a dynamic balance task.

Currently, research focuses on two different types of fatigue protocols, either short term which focuses on inducing fatigue by implementing a series of consecutive explosive repetitions such as vertical jumps, short sprints, single leg squats or double leg squats. This is combined with jumps or long term which focuses on fatiguing participants by implementing extended protocols such as 60-minute shuttle runs including walking, running and sprinting.

This study is designed to implement extended fatigue through a series of 125 club specific golf swings at 30 second intervals. Gribble et al. (2004) discovered that during a single leg stance, localised fatigue was found on postural control maintenance. This effect was greater for fatigue of the sagittal or frontal plane movers of the hip in comparison to the ankles.

A study by Ochsendorf et al. (2000) has indicated that postural sway is increased by isokinetic fatigue of the ankle plantar flexors and dorsiflexors. According to Kobriger et al. (2006) and Higdon et al. (2012) a golf player may take over 10,000 steps and swing the golf club 100 times or more during a round of golf. There is, however,

limited research that investigates the impact on a player and their performance that repeated golf swings have on lower limb muscles and fatigue.

Previous studies have reported that muscle fatigue can be linked to decreased performance in sport (Mullaney et al., 2005), (Nuño et al., 2016), (Reilly et al., 2008). Examples of this are reported by both Mullaney et al. (2005) where postgame shoulder strength tests revealed selective fatigue of 15% in shoulder flexion ($P = 0.02$), 18% fatigue in internal rotation ($P = 0.03$), and 11% fatigue in shoulder adduction ($P = 0.01$) during a baseball pitching study and Nuño et al. (2016) who shows lower ball velocity and accuracy in handball as a result of muscular fatigue.

Presently, there are few general golf fatigue studies. Higdon et al. (2012) used a golf fatiguing protocol to determine if trunk/pelvis rotation, weight transfer or body position changed and whether this had an impact on CHV and shot consistency. The study found that although there were changes in some of the biomechanical variables, the fatigue protocol highlighted a 2.5% decrease in CHV at ball contact but a 9% increase in shot consistency.

Research by Horton et al. (2001) studied the abdominal activation of 18 professional male golfers both with and without chronic lower back pain before and after a golf related fatigue protocol. The study could not conclude that the differences in abdominal activity were in fact a cause or a result of the pain. Both studies point out the need for further research in these areas which complies with Sorbie et al. (2016), who points out that the effect of muscular fatigue during the golf swing is relatively unknown in relation to performance and injury rate.

2.12. Phases of the Golf Swing

Many golf studies refer to “the phases of the golf swing”. These phases however are not directly uniformed across all studies. Generally, researchers divide the golf swing into either five or six separate phases. The studies within this thesis shall refer to the six-phase model image within this paper (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: *Silhouette Image of Golf Swing Phases*

- Address. The point where the club head is in close proximity to the ball at the start of the swing and the frame before backwards movement was initiated.
- Top of Backswing. The point in which the club head reached its most lateral position, towards the intended target, before changing direction.
- Acceleration. The point where the club achieved a horizontal position 90° from address.
- Impact. The moment the club head made impact with the ball.
- Early Follow Through. The position of the club head 180° opposite the acceleration phase (on the left of the participant).
- Late Follow Through. Position of the club head as it reaches its most lateral position from the intended target, before changing direction.

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2.13. Participants

It may be worth noting that previous studies have grouped all participants by either ability (elite, non-elite, novice, beginner) (Kawashima et al., 1998) or by handicap (Zheng et al., 2007). This can cause difficulty whilst comparing studies especially if other performance variables are not noted. Sim and Kim (2010) found that during a putting study, experts showed a reduction in movement velocity and improved accuracy in comparison to novices. However, Nesbit (2005) produced a 3D golf swing analysis of golfers with various abilities. Bradshaw (2009) has assessed golf swing variability of high and low-handicapped players, whilst Egret (2006) assessed the kinematic differences between experienced male and female golfers.

All studies found that differences in golf swing and CHV can be attributed to many different external entities, this can include skill level, sex, injury level etc. Unfortunately, in both studies the Vicon motion capture system operated at 50 Hz which, as (Bartlett, 2007) points out, is unsuitable for the quantitative study of very fast movement. This reinforces the need to increase the sampling rates (1000 Hz (Verikas et al., 2016)) during golf specific field-based research to ensure the accurate capture of data during the swing phases.

2.14. Summary

EMG research is a popular method within golf literature. These studies focus on measuring muscle activation levels within identified areas of interest, with an outcome of injury mechanisms and golf performance. To date, limited research has been conducted on forearm muscle activation during golf swings.

Similarly, to date, limited research has been conducted on the validity of golf swing related 2D AVPS. These systems possess the ability to be used in many different

environments without the need for expensive laboratories and highly trained staff. 2D systems are portable, inexpensive (some are free) and available to many without the need for specialised equipment. These 2D systems can be simply created by utilising an individuals or organisations mobile hardware (phone, camera, tablet etc) and integrating with either free or relatively inexpensive software (Kinovea, Silicon Coach etc).

Additionally, there is currently limited research on the effect that muscular fatigue has on lower limb golf kinematic performance variables. It is commonly accepted that muscles that lack endurance could represent significant risk factors with regards to injury occurrence (Lindsay et al., 2008).

There are a number of gold standard 3D motion analysis systems that have been previously used to evaluate human movement during sporting activities or rehabilitation procedures. Popular systems used for research are Qualisys and Vicon (Egret, 2003), (Tinmark et al., 2010), (Healy et al., 2011). The current project uses the Vicon Bonita motion scanning system. This system was used to capture specific movements throughout the golf swing. The Vicon Bonita system was also used to validate a golf performance measurement tool.

3. Study 1: Reliability of Forearm Muscle Electromyography Data During Multi-Planar Maximum Voluntary Contraction Grip and Wrist Articulation

3.1. Abstract

To date, the Myon 320 system has yet to be reliably tested using forearm muscles responsible for gripping. The purpose of this research is to reliably test electromyographic (EMG) signals from both the flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS) and extensor carpi radialis brevis (ECRB) muscles of both left and right arms during an individual, static multi-planar maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) hand grip task. Eight right-handed male participants performed two maximal hand grips in five separate positions for both left and right hands. Muscle activity was recorded from both forearms. There were no significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) shown whilst comparing left and right FDS or ECRB. Secondary findings noted that whilst comparing the activity from the FDS and ECRB on the same arm, the ECRB displayed an average of 3.3 times the output of the FDS ($SD \pm 0.49$). In conclusion, the protocols, methods and systems have produced valid data and results and can be used for future trials.

Keywords. EMG, Electromyography, Hand Grip, FDS, ECRB

3.2. Introduction

Handgrip strength testing has been a method widely used in various sporting contexts. The method is used by occupational therapist in a range of clinical settings, particularly in hand therapy (Fess, 1986). It is fast, easy to perform, reliable and produces results which are simple to record and analyse (Fess, 1986). Common ways to assess hand function is to measure grip strength and pinch strength (Nissenkorn and Ben-Zeev, 2012). Grip strength has become the most reliable and practical way to measure human strength which is highlighted in empirical research by Innes (1999). It is widely used in adults as an indication of strength in fitness testing in both sport and fitness (Newman et al., 1984).

Only a few studies have been carried out to determine whether grip strength has a correlation with overall body strength. Tietjen-Smith et al. (2009) found a direct correlation in grip strength and overall body strength in very elderly females. Furthermore, Fry et al. (2006) also found a correlation between grip strength and performance in American men junior weightlifting. However, Budoff (2004) confirms that grip strength is determined by many other variables and also correlate with nutritional status, weakness in the rotator cuff, fatigue, and overall physical function.

Many daily active movements and sporting skills depend on high activity levels of the flexor musculature of the forearms and hands. These are the muscles responsible for grip strength; the strength of an athlete's grip can be a key factor in injury prevention and overall strength of a developing athlete (Chen and Leung, 2007) .

Golf-related injuries involving the hand and wrist tend to take place on impact (ball/ground strike), usually affecting soft tissue, nerve or bone (Hutson and Speed, 2011).

Unfortunately, due to loss of function and ability to perform, the player may be unable to play until a full recovery has taken place. Many golfers find it difficult to refrain from playing whilst injured due to passion for the sport (Grimshaw et al., 2002).

There are various reasons as to why these types of injuries may occur. A player may possess poor swing mechanics, or they could practice to excess (Meira and Brumitt, 2010). Old or insufficiently gripped golf clubs may also increase the risk of injury (Thériault and Lachance, 1998) as well as having a tight or strong grip which may result in similar damage tears, flexor/extensor tenosynovitis, instabilities of the ligaments or triangular fibrocartilage complex injury. These are types of soft tissue injury which can be difficult to diagnose and manage due to the subtlety of the damage.

The wrist of a person's non-dominant side has a greater chance of tendinopathy occurring, especially if it demonstrates a catapulting function, together with extreme movement, (Murray and Cooney, 1996). Similar disorders to the dominant wrist can occur with radial deviation and hyperextension. Recurring subluxation of the extensor carpi ulnaris or dislocation can be the outcomes from these actions. Surgery is generally essential if the fibro-osseous sheath becomes torn either on the radial or ulnar side. Reacting to stress, bone oedema disorders, and fractures (mainly repetitive impact or acute), can happen to any bones in the wrist or hands from golf-related injuries. The hamate, or more specifically the hook of hamate is the most susceptible to stress-related injuries or isolated fractures. It is vital that diagnosis and treatment are quick with repairing the damaged hook. Stress injuries are managed conventionally with plenty of rest (Murray and Cooney, 1996).

Altering the biomechanics of the golf swing by examining muscle activity of the forearms (right and left flexor digitorum superficialis and extensor carpi radialis brevis) may not only help improve a golfer's performance but could potentially lower

their handicap. Many golfers are unaware that their grip is excessively tight when they play, thus increasing the risk of injury/recurring injury as well as possible poorer performance (Bayes and Wadsworth, 2009).

The kinematic characteristics of the wrist are obtained by analysing two significant planar motions of the hand relative to the forearm, the flexion-extension motion and radial-ulnar deviation. The functional range of motion, the looseness locus, and the instantaneous center of rotation locus are the three mechanical quantities used to describe the kinematic behavior of the wrist (Andrews and Youm, 1979). Hoffman and Strick (1999) highlights that the kinematics of the wrist are radial and ulnar deviation movements, extension movements and flexion movements.

A study by Goh et al. (2001) investigated the effect of sleep deprivation on hormonal profile and performance. The main performance measurement of this study was handgrip strength. It was found that grip performance increased during the day and declined at night and that sleep deprivation lowered performance levels. This shows that grip strength can be affected by the time of day that testing is being carried out and by the amount of rest the athlete has had (Cappaert, 1999).

A number of studies have been carried out that utilise surface EMG on many differing muscle groups. Marshall and Murphy (2003) tested reliability of a surface EMG system on abdominal muscles during rapid limb movement. Hoozemans and Van Dieën (2005) used surface EMG to assess handgrip forces during tasks involving a power grip, whilst Potvin and Bent (1997) used surface EMG signals to quantify muscle fatigue of the bicep muscles during repetitive tasks. Other studies have been carried out using a Myon 320 system.

A study by Duque et al. (1995) has captured EMG data from the forearm muscles of the right hand only whilst the wrist positions being held in the neutral, flexion, extension, radial deviation and ulnar deviation positions. The purpose of that

investigation was to reliably test and validate the electromyographic output from the forearm muscles that are responsible for gripping (the extensor carpi radialis brevis (ECRB) and the flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS)) using a JAMAR dynamometer and a MEGA ME 3000 EMG (Mega Electronics Ltd, Kuopio Finland) recorder.

The rationale behind this study stems from this research by Duque et al. (1995) which highlights the validity of an empirical mathematical formula to predict the relative forces that are exerted during a maximum handgrip in various wrist positions.

3.3. Methods

3.3.1. Ethics

The School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee at University of the West of Scotland have granted ethical approval for all studies within this thesis (Appendix 8). All participants were provided with an information sheet for this study prior to testing. (Appendix 1) and have completed a physical activity readiness questionnaire (PAR - Q) (Appendix 2) and gave written consent (Appendix 6).

3.3.2. Participants

Eight right-handed male participants participated in this laboratory-based pilot study. (Age: 22.3 ± 1.8 years, Height: 185.5 ± 5.40 cm, Body Mass: 82.1 ± 12.2 kg). Participants had no wrist or elbow injuries within a twelve-month period and no surgery in these areas over a five-year period. Each participant was attached to a custom rig (to ensure correct elbow positioning).

3.3.3. Apparatus

A Myon 320 Surface EMG System was used with AMBU surface electrodes to capture the output of the ECRB and FDS during each MVC. The Myon 320 Surface EMG system was interfaced with a Vicon Bonita motion analysis system (Oxford,

UK). The motion capture system was used to monitor the markers placed on the elbow joint and segments of the forearm and upper arm. This ensured the forearm and upper arm at the elbow joint remained at 90° for all participants during the experiment. A Medical Research Ltd pinch grip digital analyser was used to capture the force (N) of each maximal hand grip for a maximum time of five seconds.

A digital dynamometer (Medical Research Ltd digital analyser) (Figure 3.1) was required for the handgrip study of the thesis. This was used alongside the CAS (Clinical Analysis Software) software, which enabled hand grip strength analysis to take place. The dynamometer was used to perform maximum voluntary contractions (MVC) and sub-MVC from the forearm muscles that were tested throughout the research. Calibration of the dynamometer was factory performed. Unfortunately, there is currently no supportive factory calibration documentation available, however, the measurements obtained were repeatable and reliable. Although, the company documentation on calibration is not available, evidence from the web suggest that the company has been bought over by the Gym Group and their website is currently just a holding page explaining this (MIE Medical Research Ltd, 2023).

A custom rig (Figure 3.2) was created to allow for a secure, accurate and repeatable position to carry out hand grip tests. The rig has an adjustable vertical arm brace that can be moved and secured both fore and aft to ensure that each participants' hand does not rest on either the rig or the table. It can also be rotated to accommodate both left and right arms.

To ensure further stability, the arm is secured to the rig at both forearm and bicep points by Velcro straps. The Medical Research Ltd pinch/grip analyser will display the grip force in newtons, graphical and numerical analysis include maximum grip force, grip rate, fatigue rate, actual fatigue, release rate and integrated area.

Figure 3.1: *Medical Research Ltd Digital Analyser*

Figure 3.2: *UWS Constructed Test Rig with Participant*

Myon 4000 Hz analog EMG sensors (Figure 3.3) are part of the Myon system that can transmit wirelessly up to 32 muscles to a receiver unit up to 30 meters away. EMG electrodes are placed directly on the skin. Each sensor has a short cable to allow for freedom of movement. This system delivers participant comfort in terms of sensor attachment and uninterrupted participant motion.

Figure 3.3: *Myon 4000 Hz Analog EMG Sensors*

A Gigaset box (Figure 3.4) allows for multiple and synchronised connections of client PC's, force plates, EMG systems and Bonita cameras as well as referencing video and other measurement equipment. All cameras are connected by ethernet gigacables, where all other equipment can be connected with dust proof connectors.

Figure 3.4: *Giganet Smart Box*

AMBU electrodes (Figure 3.5) serve as a conduit between the EMG sensors and the participants prepared skin. These electrodes are not reusable and contain highly conductive wet gel. A combination of instant and long-term adhesives allows for excellent contact and stable signals throughout the monitoring period.

Figure 3.5: *AMBU Electrodes*

As previously mentioned, the Vicon Bonita motion analysis system was utilised in this study to accurately measure the elbow angle during each MVC. This system had a sampling rate of up to 250 Hz (Vicon Motion Systems Ltd, Oxford, UK) to provide a high-quality data capture environment. Vicon's one mega pixel camera can capture 0.5 mm of movement of 9 mm markers within a 4 m x 4 m volume.

The system has eight Vicon Nexus high resolution and high accuracy cameras (B-10 Vicon Bonita) (Figure 3.6). These are placed around the biomechanics laboratory on a custom framework, which is securely fastened to the four walls of the laboratory.

The horizontal rails of the frame were positioned approximately 1 meter and 2 meters from ground level to ensure the visualisation of the retro-reflective markers (Figure 3.10) is optimised and reduces any potential residual errors that can affect marker identification and reconstruction (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.6: *Bonita B-10 High Resolution and High Accuracy Cameras*

Figure 3.7: *Camera Positions Showing 8 Bonita 10 Cameras*

Prior to the start of every trial and before video data capture, the Vicon system had to be calibrated using the specific Vicon Active Calibration Wand (Figure 3.8) which works in tandem with Vicon's Bonita camera system. Firstly, a Vicon dynamic calibration was performed. This involved "waving the wand" as the cameras picked up the trajectories, orientation and position of the wand. Upon completion of the wand wave, the image errors on the Vicon Nexus software were observed to ensure they were small and less than 0.13. The wand was then positioned into the dedicated slots within the force plates to enable the static calibration procedure to be

implemented which involved setting the systems Global Coordinates.

This allows for a fast and accurate calibration of the entire volume area covered by the Vicon Bonita system. As the Vicon calibration wand is quite simply a cross with LEDs installed, the only calibration required for this piece of equipment is a visual inspection to ensure that all lights are illuminating.

The MX Giganet smart box was combined to create a distributed architecture that would link MX cameras and supported third-party devices. The host PC was also required to run all application software and save data collected during the trials. A Hewlett-Packard PC had the latest Vicon Nexus software installed (version 2.2.2 and 2.2.3) which contained the following system specifications including Windows 7, 64 Bit operating system, 3.7 GHz Intel processor, 8 GB ram and over 2 TB of hard drive space (Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.8: *Vicon Calibration Wand*

Figure 3.9: *Host PC Specifications*

Figure 3.10: *1.4 cm Retro-Reflective Markers*

3.3.4. EMG Procedures

Prior to testing each participant's skin was prepared for placement of the EMG AMBU surface sensors (AMBU, Cambridge, UK). This process involved hair removal from the specific areas with a disposable razor, followed by rubbing with a fine emery paper to abrade the skin before thoroughly cleaning with a hypoallergenic alcohol swab. AMBU surface sensors were then placed on the FDS and ECRB forearm muscles before connecting it to the electrode transmitters.

After capturing the data (at 1000 Hz) a high/low pass butterworth filter (High 400 Hz, Low 20 Hz) and RMS (20 ms) were implemented prior to analysis. All data was then exported to Microsoft Excel 2016 where the data from the address through to the top of the backswing was extracted and then averaged by club/fatigue status. This process was then repeated for each participant before further analysis was carried out on the average of all participants.

3.3.5. Statistical Analysis

Normal distribution for all angles was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test (McCormick et al., 2014). A null hypothesis for the tests was accepted due to all *P* values being higher than 0.05. Upon this being determined a two-way random effects model with single and average intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) measures, with their 95% confidence interval was used. This was used to measure the repeatability of the motion analysis Vicon Bonita motion analysis equipment. ICC and coefficient of variation (CV) were obtained using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS V 22.0), Jamovi (Version 2.4.8) and Microsoft Excel (Version 2010). ICC was categorised for all of the studies as follows: good validity: 0.80 to 1.00; fair validity: 0.60 to 0.79; poor validity: < 0.60 (Sleivert and Wenger, 1994). Atkinson et al. (1999) also suggests a measurement tool is reliable if the ICC is above 0.80 and the CV is below 10%. The CV was calculated as follows:

$$CV = \frac{SD}{Mean} \times 100\%$$

3.3.6. Experimental Design

Each participant performed two maximal hand grips in five separate positions (neutral, flexion, extension, radial deviation and ulnar deviation) for a maximum of five seconds with a two-minute rest period between efforts. This was then repeated

for the other hand. A Medical Research Ltd pinch grip digital analyser was used to capture the force (N) of each maximal hand grip for a maximum time of five seconds. A total of ten trials were carried out for each hand with five separate wrist positions (neutral, flexion, extension, radial deviation and ulnar deviation) and two repetitions per position.

During this trial, each participant was required to sit on a chair (height: 45 cm) and rest their forearm on a table (height: 70 cm) with their elbow fixed at 90°. Retro-reflective markers (Figure 3.10) were placed on the elbow, shoulder, and wrist to analyse any variance in elbow angle. After each MVC the participants were required to rest for five minutes to avoid muscular fatigue.

3.3.7. Initial Handgrip Reliability

During the first five participants EMG reliability study trials, it was noticed that handgrip data varied considerably across each of the three trials. These inconsistencies were observed as possibly being a result of forearm and shoulder movement during each trial.

3.3.8. Results

These initial handgrip trials displayed fair reliability [$ICC(2, 1) = 0.71$] and a high CV of 14.41% (95% CI = 4.33 - 22.90) between participants. The degree of variation in the elbow joint angle between the three trials was 5° between participants.

Figure 3.11 displays the handgrip strength test results for these initial five participants and Table 3.1 show the elbow joint angles during these initial trials.

Figure 3.11: *Handgrip Results from Participants A-E in Newtons (N)*

Table 3.1: *Vicon Angular Measurements (°)*

Participant	Trial 1 Angle Range (°)	Trial 2 Angle Range (°)	Trial 3 Angle Range (°)	CV
A	90 - 87	89 - 68	90 - 85	9.67
B	88 - 99	90 - 88	90 - 100	4.33
C	90 - 98	88 - 88	90 - 80	6.00
D	91 - 90	90 - 93	90 - 82	4.00
E	90 - 88	89 - 80	92 - 90	4.33

3.3.9. Conclusion

As a result of the inconsistencies found during test trials, a rig was constructed at the University of the West of Scotland engineering departmental workshop (Figure 3.2). The rig was created to limit the movement of the participant's arm. It was perceived, therefore, that handgrip trials would be more consistent when using the rig.

The rig was attached to the table and enabled the shoulder, elbow, and wrist to be secured and fixed in place.

3.3.10. Rig Reliability

Twelve participants were recruited to now further verify the reliability of the newly created rig and were asked to perform a total of three 5 second MVC handgrip trials with the right arm, with a 5 minute rest period between trials. These trials were performed both with the arm being strapped to the rig and with the rig removed. Grip strength was measured during each of the trials, as well as arm movement.

However, it was found that the rig now obstructed the marker attached to the elbow, this now had to be placed on the rig aligned with the elbow joint. For both protocols, the trials were performed with the participants sitting on a chair (height: 45 cm) and their forearm resting on a table (height: 70 cm), with their elbow flexed at 90°.

3.3.11. Results

The 3 trials performed with the right arm strapped to the rig displayed good reliability [$ICC(2, 1) = 0.99$] and an acceptable CV of 1.68% (95% CI = 0.46 - 3.48). The average handgrip strength between participants was 301.08 ± 4.75 N. The trials performed without the rig also displayed good reliability [$ICC(2, 1) = 0.98$] and an acceptable CV of 3.01% (95% CI = 0.91 - 6.35). On average, the elbow joint angle displayed a variation of 2.17° when the arm was strapped to the rig, and 5.92° when the arm was not strapped to the rig (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2: *Angular Movement of the Elbow Joint and Variation*

Participant	Mean Angle Range With Rig (°)	Variation (°)	Mean Angle Range Without Rig (°)	Variation (°)
A	91 - 92	1	92 - 84	8
B	90 - 89	1	89 - 94	5
C	91 - 89	2	90 - 94	4
D	90 - 89	1	91 - 87	4
E	91 - 87	4	90 - 83	7
F	90 - 90	0	93 - 87	6
G	89 - 88	1	91 - 83	8
H	92 - 88	4	90 - 87	3
I	91 - 89	2	90 - 85	5
J	89 - 85	4	89 - 95	6
K	90 - 87	3	90 - 100	10
L	91 - 88	3	90 - 95	5

3.3.12. Conclusion

The results for this study show that the two methods when recording handgrip trials of the handgrip test were reliable. However, the CV was reduced when using the rig compared to when the arm was not being secured. As a result of these findings, the rig was used when performing MVC trials from the forearm muscles.

3.3.13. Data Analysis

Data from the original eight participant trial (using the new test rig) was then sorted by participant before calculating the FDS and ECRB signal averages for each attempt. Movement means were then calculated to give an overall average of signals from both attempts of each movement. A paired t-test (Table 3.3) was also carried out to compare the differences between the four muscles (left and right FDS and ECRB) and their corresponding wrist positions. Significance was set to $P \leq 0.05$.

Table 3.3: Paired T-Test Results

T-TEST	P-Value
Lhand FDS vs Rhand FDS - Extension	0.601
Lhand FDS vs Rhand FDS - Flexion	0.453
Lhand FDS vs Rhand FDS - Neutral	0.544
Lhand FDS vs Rhand FDS - Radial Deviation	0.676
Lhand FDS vs Rhand FDS - Ulnar Deviation	0.247
Lhand ECRB vs Rhand ECRB - Extension	0.873
Lhand ECRB vs Rhand ECRB - Flexion	0.854
Lhand ECRB vs Rhand ECRB - Neutral	0.998
Lhand ECRB vs Rhand ECRB - Radial Deviation	0.848
Lhand ECRB vs Rhand ECRB - Ulnar Deviation	0.337
Lhand FDS vs Lhand ECRB - Extension	0.002
Lhand FDS vs Lhand ECRB - Flexion	< 0.001
Lhand FDS vs Lhand ECRB - Neutral	< 0.001
Lhand FDS vs Lhand ECRB - Radial Deviation	0.002
Lhand FDS vs Lhand ECRB - Ulnar Deviation	< 0.001
Rhand FDS vs Rhand ECRB - Extension	0.003
Rhand FDS vs Rhand ECRB - Flexion	0.009
Rhand FDS vs Rhand ECRB - Neutral	0.011
Rhand FDS vs Rhand ECRB - Radial Deviation	0.003
Rhand FDS vs Rhand ECRB - Ulnar Deviation	0.007

3.4. Results

All participants displayed similar trends with their EMG output from both forearm muscle groups throughout the five tests for both arms. The MVC's of each wrist position (extension, flexion, radial deviation and ulnar deviation) have been averaged and then calculated as a percentage of the neutral mean for both arms.

There were no significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) shown across different muscle groups on the same arm (left FDS vs left ECRB and right FDS vs right ECRB). However, a significant difference was displayed across the same muscle groups on opposite arms (left FDS vs right FDS and right ECRB vs left ECRB) see Figure 3.12.

3.4.1. Flexor Digitorum Superficialis

Output from both left and right FDS muscles displayed no significant difference across all five wrist positions (extension $P = 0.601$; flexion $P = 0.453$; neutral $P = 0.544$; radial deviation $P = 0.676$; ulnar deviation $P = 0.247$). On average, the greater muscle activation was displayed by the right FDS during the ulnar deviation wrist position (122% of the Manual Muscle Test (MMT)). The least activation was shown when the left wrist was in the radial Deviation position (72.78% of the MMT).

3.4.2. Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis

The ECRB muscle displayed an average of 3.3 times the output of the FDS ($SD \pm 0.49$). This shows that whilst there is little difference when comparing left and right FDS or ECRB across extension, flexion, neutral and radial deviation, a larger output can be seen from the right output in comparison with the left output during the ulnar deviation position.

Figure 3.12: Mean of Muscle Type by Position

3.5. Discussion

The results of this study have clearly shown that there is no significant difference in EMG output across either the FDS or ECRB when comparing the same muscle on both left and right side during different wrist positions. There is however a significant difference when comparing the FDS against the ECRB on the same arm. This pilot study concludes that the data retrieved from all participants have been validated and these protocols, methods and system can be used in future trials. This concurs with Snijders et al. (1987) who suggest that a power grip is associated to the high loading of extensor muscles. It has also been noted that this increase was not only significant with the wrist in the extension position, but also in neutral and flexion. Again, Snijders et al. (1987) support these findings by commenting that the grasping hand in the fingers cause a flexing moment at the wrist joint in various situations, which must be equilibrated by the activity of the extensor muscles.

3.6. Conclusion

This pilot study was undertaken to reliably test EMG signals using the Myon 320 sEMG System (Myon AG, Switzerland) taken from both the FDS and ECRB muscles of both left and right arms during an individual, static multi-planar MVC handgrip task. The study has highlighted that achieving reliability for normalised RMS sEMG during the tests is entirely possible. The study produced a fair reproducibility from the flexor and extensor muscles, which agrees with previous studies. The intra-session ICC analysis gave good to excellent results with the remaining results possibly benefiting by ensuring that future participants are prevented from knowing their force data during the trials and therefore preventing intrinsic competition.

Wrist position correlations within and between the FDS and ECRB muscles may be influenced by hand dominance. Results from the study indicate that the data sets retrieved from all participants were reliably evaluated. With minor adjustments to the protocols used (removal of intrinsic competition), the findings from the study demonstrate that the methods and systems outlined here can be used reliably in future experimental and clinical trials.

4. Study 2: An Evaluation of Temporal and Club Angle Parameters During Golf Swings Using Low-Cost Video Analyses Packages

4.1. Abstract

Two dimensional (2D) low cost, augmented video-based portable systems (AVPS) are commonly utilised in clinical human movement assessments and in sports coaching environments. The validity of the AVPS against the gold standard 3D-Vicon motion analysis system has been previously demonstrated. The purpose of this study was to compare swing time and golf club angle parameters during golf swings using three, 2D low cost, AVPS (Kinovea, Siliconcoach Pro, Siliconcoach Live). Twelve right-handed golfers performed three golf swings whilst being recorded by a high-speed 2D video camera. All footages were then analysed using three AVPS-software packages and the results compared using both descriptive and inferential statistics. There were no significant differences for swing time ($P = 0.763$, $F = 0.099$) with only the acceleration golf phase measurement ($P = 0.018$, $F = 5.718$) showing significance between the 2D and 3D software comparisons. The results showed a high intra class correlation coefficient ($ICC > 0.929$) and Cronbach's coefficient alpha ($CCA > 0.924$) reliability for both the kinematic and temporal parameters. Irrespective of the AVPS software investigated, the cost effective AVPS can produce reliable output measures that benefit golf analyses.

4.2. Introduction

Historically, kinesiological analyses of performances have been evaluated in both clinical (Ugbolue et al., 2013), (Zult et al., 2019), (Schurr et al., 2017) and sport (van der Kruk and Reijne, 2018) environments using low cost two-dimensional (2D) and expensive three-dimensional (3D) photogrammetry kits. It is well known that 3D motion capture is regarded as the gold standard for human movement analyses (Munro et al., 2012), (Nakagawa et al., 2014). However, it is expensive and imposes financial costs affordable by very few researchers and coaches. With the advent of digital and mobile technology, clinical-based, laboratory-based and field-based kinesiological data can be captured, processed, and analysed using bespoke 2D augmented video-based portable systems (AVPS).

Ugbolue and colleagues have captured and evaluated clinical datasets using both 2D and 3D motion systems (Ugbolue et al., 2013), (Yang et al., 2019). This has been supported by previous studies on 3D sport related projects in the area of golf swing biomechanics (Sorbie et al., 2019), (Sorbie et al., 2018) and 2D golf swing related projects (Sorbie et al., 2016). The fact remains, 2D motion systems are the next best alternative when 3D motion systems are unavailable. While few sport related field events can be 3D motion assessed within the laboratory there is still need from a practical, training, rehabilitation, and coaching perspective to be able to understand the mechanics and techniques associated with performance using advanced 2D motion systems. These concerns suggest the need for effective 2D motion system sport related alternatives that can capture slow and fast-paced dynamic and complex multiple planar motions.

The introduction of technology in sports training and coaching remains impactful and globally continues to play a significant role in the development of sport (Sherwood and Drane, 2015). The versatility of 2D video technology in sport using high-speed video has previously been investigated (Kryger et al., 2019), (Park and Logan, 2013) and remains an inexpensive solution for motion analysis that is relevant in everyday elite coaching and training sessions. Kwon et al. (2010) suggested that due to the golf swing being a complex skill of motion analysis, advanced methods of analysis are required to determine unique aspects of the skill. These advanced analysis methods include, detecting the exact instant of impact, definition of the athlete's body and the golf club in various frames and the determination of different planes of the club during the swing.

Several software products are available to analyse the 2D output from an AVPS. More products that are popular include Siliconcoach Pro, Siliconcoach Live and Kinovea. In many cases these 2D software systems are used not only for simple gait analysis but also for analysis of many sports related movements especially golf. McDonald et al. (2011) have developed a methodology to measure core ability in healthy athletes using Siliconcoach. Linn and Porter (2012) used Siliconcoach Live to evaluate wheelchair basketball players and Aprilo et al. (2022) used Kinovea to analyse tennis spin serves.

A study by Cronin et al. (2006) used Siliconcoach to assess the dynamic range of motion of the knee joint. They concluded that Siliconcoach was beneficial in the determination of the end range of static and dynamic motion, and valuable from a functional and cost-effective perspective especially within the clinical environment.

Comparable AVPS devices have also been deemed acceptable for use within clinical settings as they produce similar results to that of the Vicon motion system. This is an area of importance because it will allow smaller clinics to use the AVPS as a viable replacement to the more expensive system. This may allow rehabilitation costs to be reduced for the same results leading to less financial expenditure to both the patient and the clinics' running costs (Cronin et al., 2006). Although 2D AVPS are acceptable within the clinical and sports settings, many of the accompanying software products appear to provide inaccuracies in their temporal and spatial output measures (Ugbolue et al., 2013).

These inaccuracies predominantly are initiated and driven by the users' inability to identify the correct frames for measurement and the implementation of the accurate application of the software tools. Furthermore, these inaccuracies may lead to temporal and spatial variations and errors in the output measures. Therefore, there is a need to evaluate popular software products that are used by clinicians, coaches and biomechanists during their routine 2D video assessments. This knowledge gap raises questions as it is unclear whether significant variations exist between software products relating to the output measures reported.

There is a highlighted area of importance throughout the literature, which states that the need for rehabilitation clinics is increasing (McDonald et al., 2011). Previous research has identified that the AVPS is accurate within its own surroundings but may present problems for rehabilitation purposes when compared against the gold standard systems. The AVPS can also become more important during the analysis of golf swings as it can be used to help identify the possible causes of injury.

Even though the golf swing is not particularly intensive or exhausting, it still stresses the skeletal-muscle systems, which can be related to golf injuries such as neck, shoulder and back pain (Puig-Diví et al., 2019), (Balsalobre-Fernández et al., 2013). These injuries potentially could influence changes in movement patterns, lumbar spinal loading and muscle activity in relation to the mechanical movement of the golf swing (Pueo et al., 2020).

Despite thousands of articles dealing with analysis of golf performance, it has been identified that the game of golf remains physically and mentally complex (Balsalobre-Fernández et al., 2013). Biomechanical analysis of a golf swing is widely known as being difficult to interpret due to the complexity of the swing, as it has a 3D motion, multi-planar sequence, which is performed at great speed. There are numerous kinetics and kinematic variables that can be explored when analysing a golf swing to understand its mechanical complexity (Sabino et al., 2021). The main 2D aspects of a golf swing can be broken down into several segments, for example, how a player stands at address, weight shift during back swing and acceleration, wrist hinge angles, club release angles and torques of the shoulders and wrists throughout the swing.

These aspects all contribute to the performance of a golf swing (Littrell and Selgrade, 2018). Furthermore, Kwon et al. (2010) states that due to the golf swing being a complex skill of motion analysis, advanced methods of analyses are needed to determine unique aspects of the skill. These advanced analysis methods include detecting the exact instant of impact, definition of the athlete's body and the golf club in various frames and the determination of different planes of the club during the swing.

While some discrepancies in measurement techniques may have consequential effects on temporal and spatial output measures from a software user perspective, clarity and reassurances are needed to show the viability and robustness of the 2D AVPS in the context of temporal and joint angle measurements. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of the AVPS as a useful assessment tool for measuring golf swing time and club angle parameters using three commercial popular software namely Kinovea, Siliconcoach Pro and Siliconcoach Live. We hypothesise that there will be no significant differences between the three commercial software packages; and no significant differences between temporal outputs from the commercial software and the software from the gold standard motion analysis system.

4.3. Methods

4.3.1. Participants

Twelve right-handed participants (Male: 6, Age: 23.3 ± 4.3 years, Mass: 88.3 ± 16.6 kg, Height: 180.5 ± 4.4 cm; Female: 6, Age: 21.8 ± 1.7 years, Mass: 65.2 ± 5.7 kg, Height: 165.9 ± 8.1 cm) participated in this laboratory-based study. All participants completed a physical activity readiness questionnaire and consent form and were required to be healthy and injury free. No previous experience of playing golf was required (experience ranged from novice through to elite players). The ethics committee of the University of the West of Scotland approved the study (approval number: 5-3-14-002).

4.3.2. Apparatus

The laboratory testing area was set up in conformance to the Clinical Movement Analysis Society of UK and Ireland (CMAS) standard. A capture volume of approximately 4.8 m³ (length 2.0 m, breadth 1.2 m, height 2.0 m) was created using appropriate camera settings for analysis of the golf swing.

During all golf tests, all clubs were fitted with retro-reflective markers (Figure 4.1) This enabled the researcher to identify specific sections of the golf swing during the analysis stage. These markers were inserted into the custom golf plugin marker set.

Figure 4.1: *Example of Golf Club with Marker Placement*

TaylorMade Speed Blade 7-irons (Basingstoke, Hampshire, United Kingdom) (Figure 4.2) were used throughout the golf related studies. The 7-irons were all of standard length and lie with steel shafts attached. The 7-irons also had Golf Pride grips attached to the end of the shaft.

Figure 4.2: *TaylorMade Speed Blade 5,7 and 9-Iron*

During all golf tests, all clubs were fitted with retro-reflective markers (Figure 3.10) This enabled the researcher to identify specific sections of the golf swing during the analysis stage. These markers were inserted into the custom golf plugin marker set. To prevent damage within the lab and to ensure the safety of both participants and researchers a large four walled golf practice net (Figure 4.5) has been erected. A large artificial golf practice mat (Figure 4.3) has also been implemented to assist the participants by allowing the use of a flexible tee and to help protect the laboratory floor and clubs.

Figure 4.3: *Artificial Golf Practice Matting*

Foam practice golf balls have been used to minimize the risk of injury to both participants and researchers (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4: *Foam Practice Balls*

To ensure absolute safety throughout the golf trials in the biomechanics laboratory, an Artificial Golf Striking Mat (Longridge, United Kingdom) and a Tunnel Super Net (GolfNets, Bristol, UK) were used (Figure 4.5). Golf balls used during each testing session were Titleist Pro – V1 (Titleist, Cambridgeshire, UK). Golf swings from the driver were struck from a golf tee placed on the golf mat (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.5: *Practice Golf Net*

Prior to the commencement of each trial, a reliability and validity protocol was performed using the Vicon Bonita motion analysis system and a goniometer. The purpose of this study was to ensure the 3D motion analysis system was producing the correct angles. To enable the researchers to carry out this study, measurements were recorded from a goniometer. Retro-reflective markers were used to track the change in degree of the goniometer (Figure 4.6). The Vicon calibration wand was also used to calibrate the Vicon system (as with study one).

This was positioned on the force plate to set the global coordinates of the system and then moved around the laboratory to ensure correct vision from all cameras. The calibration enables the software to calculate the relative location and orientation of all the cameras.

Figure 4.6: *Goniometer with Retro-Reflective Markers*

Kinematic descriptions of human movement can provide a valuable objective measurement for assessing human performance and function (Melton et al., 2011). 3D motion analysis is a non-invasive method of accurately measuring the movement of the human body. Retro-reflective markers are positioned on specific landmarks of the body or object, and movement is measured using infrared cameras that capture the continual position of the markers. These positions are used to create a computer-generated model of the movement being executed.

This computer model is also used to accurately calculate human joint angles in the anatomical position, Z = superior/inferior, X = anterior/posterior, Y = lateral/medial axis. Additionally, the computer model can also calculate the velocity and acceleration of the movement. The researcher has designed a custom golf model to enable analysis of the human body as well as the golf club movements and velocities. The golf model (Figure 4.7) has been modified from the standard plug-in-gait full body model, which integrated the new golf club marker set (four extra markers placed on the club). The lower body Vicon markers that will be used during this project can be found in Table 4.1. The same computer system has been used for both this study and the EMG reliability study (Study One).

Figure 4.7: *Vicon Lower Body Golf Marker Set*

Table 4.1: *Names and Vicon Abbreviations of Marker Set*

Abbreviation	Name
LASI	Left Anterior Iliac Spine
LPSI	Left Posterior Iliac Spine
LTHI	Left Thigh
LKNE	Left Knee
LTIB	Left Tibia
LANK	Left Ankle
LHEE	Left Heel
LTOE	Left Toe
RASI	Right Anterior Iliac Spine
RPSI	Right Posterior Iliac Spine
RTHI	Right Thigh
RKNE	Right Knee
RTIB	Right Tibia
RANK	Right Ankle
RHEE	Right Heel

4.3.3. Experimental Design and Protocol

Prior to placing markers and capturing the video data, the following participant anthropometric measurements were collected:

Shoulder offset: The term otherwise referred to as the lateral glenohumeral offset can be defined as the perpendicular distance from the base of the coracoid process to the most lateral extent of the greater tuberosity. The lateral glenohumeral offset averages approximately 5.4 cm to 5.7 cm (range 4.3 cm to 6.8 cm).

Elbow width: The distance between the medial and lateral epicondyles of the humerus.

Wrist width: The distance between the anterior (palm side) and posterior (back) side of the wrist in the anatomical position.

Hand thickness: The distance between the dorsal and palmar surfaces of the hand.

Leg length: Measured from the ASIS to the medial malleolus. If a patient cannot straighten his/her legs, take the measurement in two pieces: ASIS to knee and knee to medial malleolus.

Knee width: Measurement of the knee width about the flexion axis.

Ankle width: Measurement of the ankle width about the medial and lateral malleoli.

Following the anthropometric measurements being completed, 1.4 cm retro-reflective markers (Figure 3.10) were placed on the participant and both dynamic and static calibration was captured to ensure an accurate global reference frame is established.

The golf mat and driving net were placed in the centre of the biomechanics laboratory. One 2D camera was placed in the frontal plane of the participant to ensure that the full motion of the golf swing was captured. To ensure consistency throughout the recording of all trials, a visible mark was placed on the floor behind the golf mat to indicate the stance/starting position of each participant prior to data collection. Each participant performed their own warm up procedures prior to the test and when comfortable, performed three recorded golf swings.

The 2D camera (EXILIM, Casio, USA) was mounted on a tripod at a height of 1 m, positioned at 4 m relative to the golfer and set to record at 240fps to allow for successful video capture during the high-speed movement. Four evenly spaced retro-reflective markers were placed on the shaft of the 7-iron golf club to identify the phases of the golf swing. The golf ball was covered with retro-reflective material, its position was standardised and not placed on a tee. Other retro-reflective markers were placed on the segments and joints of the lower limb of the golfers following the Plug-in-Gait model.

All 2D video data was transferred from the camera to the laptop before being analysed with Siliconcoach Live (www.siliconcoach.com/SiliconcoachLIVE), Siliconcoach Pro (www.siliconcoach.com/siliconcoachPro) and Kinovea (version 0.8.15, www.kinovea.org) software for all participant's golf swings. These three systems all have video playback features and drawing tools which can interpret joint and club angles, zoom in and out features as well as markers to show where the data was analysed on the video timeline.

The golf club inclination angle ($^{\circ}$) was calculated at each of the six golf phases (address, top of back swing, acceleration, impact, early follow through and late follow through) (Figure 2.2). The golf club inclination angle ($^{\circ}$) was calculated as the club angle with respect to the vertical.

The total golf swing phase time (swing time) was also calculated for each of the software packages. The inclination angle on the 3D Vicon motion system was similarly calculated by recording the coordinates of the positions of the golf clubs retro-reflective markers from the end of the address phase to the end of the follow through phase. To minimise inter-rater errors, the same experienced researcher defined the golf phases and digitised the markers across the software and participants.

4.3.4. Statistical Analysis

The average of three trials was determined for all participants and expressed as a function of the golf phases of measurement using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Standard error of the mean (SEM) was used to quantify the absolute consistency of the measurement (Shishov et al., 2021), while the standard error of measurement (SM) estimated the amount of error in the test. Both the SEM and SM were calculated with respect to the swing time and each golf phase of measurement. Coefficient of determination and Pearson product moment correlation coefficients were used to assess linear relationships between the 2D and 3D displacement golf club inclination angle ($^{\circ}$) measurements in the frontal plane with respect the phases of golf swing. The strength of the correlation (r) was interpreted as poor (0 to 0.49), moderate (0.50 to 0.75), and strong (> 0.75) (Beulens et al., 2020). Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS V 22.0) was used to perform a repeated measures ANOVA with a post hoc main effects comparison using the Bonferroni

correction. This was applied to establish (a) if there were any significant differences between the three commercial software instruments and (b) whether there were any significant differences between the temporal outputs from the commercial software and the Vicon motion system gold standard. Reliability of the 2D and 3D output measures were assessed using the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) and Cronbach's coefficient alpha (CCA) analyses. Statistical significance was denoted as $P \leq 0.05$.

4.4. Results

The Vicon system displayed a strong correlation with the goniometer measurement device with regards to the test-retest angle of variation. The repeated measures on the X-axis displayed good validity [$ICC(2, 1) = 1.00$] and an acceptable CV of 0.08%. The Y-axis also displayed good validity [$ICC(2, 1) = 0.99$] and an acceptable CV of 0.17%. Finally, the Z-axis displayed good validity [$ICC(2, 1) = 0.99$] and an acceptable CV of 0.08%. Figures 3.11 - 3.13 display the R-Squared values on the X, Y and Z-Axis.

Figure 4.8: Plot of Vicon Against Goniometer Measurements (X Axis)

Figure 4.9: Plot of Vicon Against Goniometer Measurements (Y Axis)

Figure 4.10: Plot of Vicon Against Goniometer Measurements (Z Axis)

The descriptive statistics for the temporal and phase measurement parameters are displayed in (Table 4.2). The swing times were very close as indicated by the sizes of the mean and standard deviation for each of the commercial software. The SEM for all three AVPS showed the same output of 0.11. However, the SM showed a

small deviation across the three AVPS with Kinovea showing a 0.01s reduction when compared to the Siliconcoach Pro and Siliconcoach Live packages.

The swing time outputs were very similar to the gold standard (Vicon Nexus 2.8.1 Software). The repeated measures ANOVA results revealed no significant differences ($P = 0.763$, $F = 0.099$) for the within-participants effects and no significant differences ($P > 0.502$) for each of the pairwise comparisons.

Apart from the acceleration ($P = 0.018$, $F = 5.718$) golf phase measurement, no significant differences were observed for the repeated measures ANOVA results between the software and the phases of the golf swing at address ($P = 0.148$, $F = 2.232$); top of backswing ($P = 0.699$, $F = 0.169$); impact ($P = 0.835$, $F = 0.175$); and follow through (late) ($P = 0.281$, $F = .346$). All pairwise comparisons are shown in (Table 4.3).

Both 2D and 3D motion analysis systems showed low levels of intra-participant variability in all kinematic and temporal variables as indicated by the size of the standard deviations across the three trials. The results showed a high intra-rater reliability for both the kinematic and temporal parameters. With respect to swing time and golf phases, the ICC value for the intra-rater reliability test was 0.929 for the swing time and ranged from 0.963 to 0.999 for the kinematic golf phase variables. The CCA reliability statistics produced a value of 0.924 for the swing time and a range from 0.961 to 0.999 for the kinematic golf phase variables.

Table 4.2: Summary of Club Angle with Respect to Vertical (°) & Swing Time (s)

Measurement	Commercial Software Product															
	Kinovea				SiliconCoach Pro				SiliconCoach Live				Vicon Nexus 2.8.1 Software			
	Mean	SD	SEM	SM	Mean	SD	SEM	SM	Mean	SD	SEM	SM	Mean	SD	SEM	SM
Swing Time (s)	1.95	0.37	0.11	0.14	1.97	0.38	0.11	0.15	1.99	0.38	0.11	0.15	1.97	0.33	0.10	0.15
Address (°)	6.70	1.91	0.55	0.44	6.24	1.51	0.43	0.34	6.78	1.90	0.55	0.43	6.57	1.70	0.49	0.40
Top of Backswing (°)	103.83	28.58	8.25	3.22	102.82	29.00	8.37	3.27	102.59	28.90	8.34	3.26	103.08	28.47	8.22	3.25
Acceleration (°)	75.38	2.98	0.86	2.01	74.03	3.56	1.03	2.40	74.19	2.83	0.82	2.27	74.53	3.01	0.87	2.23
Impact (°)	7.22	1.93	0.56	0.87	7.34	1.27	0.37	0.58	7.40	1.87	0.54	1.36	7.32	1.60	0.46	0.94
Follow Through (°)	92.96	45.52	13.14	19.26	93.23	44.67	12.89	18.90	91.68	45.35	13.09	20.28	92.62	45.14	13.03	19.48

Table 4.3: Coefficient of Determination, Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient, and Associated 95% Confidence Intervals Between 2D and 3D Analysis. Statistical Significance Level Set to $P < 0.05$

Product Comparison	Phases of the Golf Swing																			
	Address				Top of Backswing				Acceleration				Impact				Follow Through (Late)			
	r^2	r	P	95% CI	r^2	r	P	95% CI	r^2	r	P	95% CI	r^2	r	P	95% CI	r^2	r	P	95% CI
Kinovea vs Pro	0.867	0.931	0.347	-0.236, 1.153	0.997	0.998	0.363	-0.541, 2.570	0.912	0.955	0.010 *	0.306, 2.411	0.648	0.805	1.000	-1.220, 0.970	0.994	0.997	1.000	-3.585, 3.030
Kinovea vs Live	0.817	0.904	1.000	-0.849, 0.699	0.888	0.942	1.000	-7.787, 10.266	0.731	0.855	0.103	-0.173, 2.556	0.717	0.847	1.000	-1.161, 0.794	0.995	0.997	1.000	-1.583, 4.145
Pro vs Live	0.606	0.778	0.901	-1.639, 0.573	0.898	0.948	1.000	-8.449, 8.899	0.761	0.872	1.000	-1.886, 1.553	0.716	0.846	1.000	-1.027, 0.910	0.993	0.996	1.000	-1.986, 5.103
Vicon vs Kinovea	0.977	0.988	1.000	-0.449, 0.199	0.985	0.992	1.000	-3.933, 2.454	0.958	0.979	0.004 *	-1.438, -0.279	0.898	0.948	1.000	-0.505, 0.705	0.999	0.999	1.000	-2.024, 1.362
Vicon vs Pro	0.876	0.936	0.441	-0.207, 0.874	0.989	0.994	1.000	-2.581, 3.131	0.952	0.976	0.477	-0.330, 1.330	0.847	0.920	1.000	-0.631, 0.581	0.998	0.999	1.000	-2.691, 1.475
Vicon vs Live	0.889	0.943	1.000	-0.812, 0.412	0.952	0.976	1.000	-5.390, 6.390	0.878	0.937	1.000	-0.642, 1.309	0.915	0.957	1.000	-0.630, 0.464	0.998	0.999	0.749	-0.884, 2.784

4.5. Discussion

The purpose of this study was to evaluate and compare the gold standard golf club angle and swing time parameters during golf swings using three, 2D low cost, augmented video-based portable systems (Kinovea, Siliconcoach Pro, Siliconcoach Live). The findings of this study suggest that all three AVPS can be used to effectively calculate club angle parameters and swing time. The results agree with the swing time hypothesis and partially with the club angle output hypothesis where significant differences were observed for the acceleration golf phase measurement.

Although the study involved 'novice' participants, a large proportion of the acceleration golf phase measurements fell under the standard 90° inclination angle measurement. To date, this is the first study that has used multiple low cost 2D AVPS to evaluate and compare the club angle parameters and the swing time of a golf swing. While there are no recent studies that show 2D motion analysis for a golf swing, (Wright, 2008) provides a detailed historical perspective and description of motion capture technologies and methodologies that have influenced golf biomechanics, club fitting, coaching and golf instruction (Nitayarak and Charntaraviroj, 2021). Furthermore, Morrison et al. (2014) also provide useful information that could benefit coaches.

Biomechanical analysis of a golf swing is widely known as being difficult to interpret due to the complexity of the swing, as it has a 3D motion, multi-planar sequence, which is performed at very high speeds (Sabino et al., 2021).

Many software systems available allow for the evaluation of movement. These software systems vary in cost and can be delivered across multiple platforms (PC, phone, tablet), or via the server, web or client base.

This study has taken a subset of these systems, Kinovea (free PC based application), Siliconcoach Pro (purchased PC based application) and Siliconcoach Live (purchased web-based application) and compared their outputs. The environment in which these applications may be used can differ, but the importance of the validity of the results remains the same. As a limitation, our sample size was small; however, this study has shown that the AVPS can produce a reliable and valid output with little financial overheads.

The analysis benefitted from the reliability statistical measurements i.e., the ICC and CCA analysis producing reliability results comparable to the clinical study done by (Ugbolue et al., 2013). Future studies may choose to use only amateur golfers or perhaps professional golfers with a low handicap. This may also show greater reliability and validity as their base technical model may display greater consistency across all swings. Finally, the use of 2D AVPS software packages should be encouraged among movement analysis researchers and coaches, particularly when 3D motion capture systems and software cannot be accessed.

4.6. Conclusion

Overall, the results from the three software packages were close as reflected by the descriptive statistics including the SEM and SM results. Further analyses revealed no significant differences for the ANOVA results with respect to the measured phases of the golf swing. High intra-rater reliability and CCA kinematic and temporal parameter measurements were obtained.

These results challenge the debate surrounding the purported errors and inaccuracies associated with the 2D AVPS. 2D AVPS are therefore useful, cost effective, easy to operate, reliable and indeed accurate when used correctly and in accordance with the recommended protocol instructions and guidelines. Given the outcome of our results, it is envisaged coaches, clinicians and biomechanics researchers will be reassured and encouraged to use the 2D AVPS where possible for their movement analysis assessments and evaluations.

5. Study 3: Effect of Fatigue on Hip, Knee and Ankle Proprioception During a Golf Specific Fatigue Protocol

5.1. Abstract

The purpose of this pilot study is to determine whether muscle fatigue generated by a golf specific fatiguing protocol will have an effect on proprioception and kinematic parameters of both left and right hip knee and ankle joints. Thirteen healthy, right-handed male participants participated in this pilot study (Height 177.48 ± 10.61 cm, Body Mass 71.24 ± 14.09 kg) respectively. These participants were asked to perform 125 golf swings using various clubs whilst being recorded with a 3D motion capture system. A subset of swings were calculated as pre-fatigue and post fatigue for evaluation purposes. All data was then analysed, and the results compared using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The results of this study show that although there is no significant difference displayed for the Y and Z axis of the right knee angle during all phases with both clubs as well as the 7-iron at the top of the backswing for all joint angles. There are significant differences throughout the remainder of the swing/joint angles with this increasing during the faster phases of the swing and/or with the shorter 7-iron club. Significant differences in t-tests have also been noted in many of the fatigued results when comparing clubs as well as lower associations during a Pearson correlation coefficient during all fatigued figures whilst measuring by club, and 7-iron when measuring by fatigue status. Whilst this may indicate a fatigue effect during golf swings, the author feels that further investigation is required.

Keywords: Golf, Kinematic, Fatigue, 3D Motion Analysis

5.2. Introduction

The golf swing is a complex movement of the whole body that encompasses the sagittal, frontal, and transverse planes (Higdon et al., 2012), (Kanwar et al., 2021), (McHugh et al., 2022). A number of golf related studies have been carried out to improve performance in this field with regards to physical conditioning, mood, injury prevention and swing mechanics. The purpose of this pilot study is to determine whether muscle fatigue generated by a golf specific fatiguing protocol will have an effect on proprioception and kinematic parameters of both left and right hip, knee and ankle joints during the six phases of the golf swing.

5.3. Fatigue

Gibson and Edwards (2012) describes fatigue as the transient inability to maintain power output or force during repeated muscle contractions. According to studies by Lucci et al. (2011) and Miller and Bird (1976) hip and knee mechanics can be substantially altered whilst fatigued. However, Higdon et al. (2012) points out that “golf specific fatigue did not relate to the initial lower body sagittal plane angles at address nor was simulated golf specific fatigue related to peak transverse plane pelvis and trunk rotational velocities (or their timings) in a manner that indicates a relationship to resultant club head velocity and shot consistency”. Rozzi et al. (1999) notes that fatigue can be regarded as the main component that affects the musculoskeletal system because of its relationship with reduction in knee proprioception and increase in joint laxity. Laboratory studies have shown that the neuromuscular control of the lower limb is compromised in the fatigued state (Hiemstra et al., 2001).

Johnston et al. (1998) found that participants had a significantly decreased ability to maintain balance on one or both legs after fatiguing the lower limbs to less than

50% of original strength values. Wojtys et al. (1996) found that a fatiguing protocol on a dynamometer delayed voluntary muscle reaction time, decreased firing rates of the hamstrings and quadriceps as well as delaying spinal reflexes. Studies by Carpenter et al. (2016), Pedersen et al. (1999), McCloskey (1973) and Taimela et al. (1999) have also shown similar effects in the shoulder, elbow and lumbar spine.

Salavati et al. (2007) have found that fatigue of the proximal lower extremity muscles can affect postural stability and fatigue of the frontal movers and can be associated with postural instability in the frontal plane. Miller and Bird (1976) consider the knee and hip flexors/extensors as the most important muscle group for performance on a dynamic balance task. Gribble et al. (2004) discovered that during a single leg stance, localised fatigue was found on postural control maintenance. This effect was greater for fatigue of the sagittal or frontal plane movers of the hip in comparison to the ankles. A study by Ochsendorf et al. (2000) has indicated that postural sway is increased by isokinetic fatigue of the ankle plantar flexors and dorsiflexors.

Currently, research focuses on two different types of fatigue protocols either short term, which focuses on inducing fatigue by implementing a series of consecutive explosive repetitions such as vertical jumps, short sprints, single leg squats or double leg squats combined with jumps, or long term which focuses on fatiguing participants by implementing extended protocols such as 60-minute shuttle runs which includes walking, running, and sprinting.

This study is designed to implement extended fatigue through a series of 125 club specific golf swings at 30 second intervals.

5.4. Biomechanics of the Golf Swing

The “perfect” swing is every golfer’s ultimate goal. Every time the ball is addressed, a combination of factors can have an impact on the flight of the ball and the outcome of the shot. From this point, the forces within the golf swing should be structured to ensure the club head should arrive back at the same point prior to impact at the correct velocity, position, direction, angle of attack and orientation to ensure the correct flight path of the ball is achieved. A study by Hume et al. (2005) points out that coaches look for consistent and mechanically sound movements with their participants swings, but many previous investigations focus primarily on the increase in shot distance (primarily with the driver).

Suttie (2006) describes this as a consistent swing that will deliver the clubface to the ball at the point of impact, in a square alignment to the target line at maximal velocity and the clubface being perfectly vertical.

These skilled actions are described by Bril et al. (2010) as a comprise of a combination of flexibility, precision, adaptability, smoothness, regularity, optimisation, and swiftness. Hume et al. (2005) describe golf biomechanics as the principles and technique of mechanics to the structure and function of the golfer. Specifically, golf biomechanics examines movement characteristics of the swing as well as the resultant joint forces and patterns of muscle activity; thus, biomechanical analysis of an elite player’s swing should allow a better understanding of optimal swing mechanics (McCarroll et al., 2016).

According to Maddalozzo (1987) the ball should be positioned at the lowest point of the full swing. This should be left of the target line center and towards the left inside heel (right-handed players). When addressing the ball, posture and alignment can

directly affect the swing plane and club head pathway. Alignment can also affect the transfer of weight and balance during the swing (Kirby and Roberts 1985).

Newell and Corocos (1993) have suggested that variability of movement can regularly be viewed as noise (disturbance) within the central nervous system and should be classified as dysfunctional. However, Williams, and Davids (2005) note that the movement variability is intrinsic within a skilled motor performance and allows the performers adaption and flexibility in their environment. Many studies have investigated methods of increasing power, distance and accuracy of a golf swing. Fradkin et al. (2004) have investigated warmups, (Tuxen, 2009) the angle of attack as well as Vengellow and Santiago (2008) who established the correct clubs for different golfing populations.

5.5. Methods

5.5.1. Participants

Thirteen healthy, right-handed male participants participated in this pilot study (Height 177.8 ± 10.61 cm, Body Mass 71.24 ± 14.09 kg) respectively. Prior to the experiment, a physical activity readiness questionnaire and consent form were completed. Participants were required not to participate in any conditioning or resistance training 48 hours prior to the study and were informed of the format of the practice session. They were also advised that they could stop and remove themselves from the study at any time. The study did not require any previous golf background. The participants golfing abilities ranged from novice through to elite. The University of the West of Scotland, School of Science and Sport ethics committee granted ethical approval for the study to take place (Appendix 8).

5.5.2. Apparatus

This study shared many of the apparatus and validation protocols from previous EMG and AVPS validation (studies one and two of this thesis). These include the use of foam golf balls, practice golf net and an artificial golf practicing mat to minimise injury to both participants and researchers, whilst providing additional protection to the laboratory floor and retro-reflective marked golf clubs. In addition to the previously used 7-iron clubs, this study also utilised a TaylorMade SLDR driver (Basingstoke, Hampshire, United Kingdom) (Figure 5.1). The driver was of a standard length and lie angle, with a graphite shaft attached. The driver also had a golf pride grip attached to the end of the shaft.

Figure 5.1: *TaylorMade SLDR Driver used During the Fatigue Study*

The previously utilised computer hardware and software were also used in conjunction with the Vicon Bonita system to avoid any conflicts or errors due to the implementation of new technology.

All setup and validation protocols have also been reused from the previous studies as again, these have been previously successful with the current technologies.

5.5.3. Experimental Design and Protocol

An enclosed golf driving net (Sports Net Company, United Kingdom) (Figure 4.5) and artificial golf mat (Longridge, United Kingdom) (Figure 4.3) were placed in the

centre of the laboratory, with the mat being placed in front of the AMTI OR6 Series force plates. Markers were placed on the floor to ensure a consistent starting position during each attempt throughout the trial. Each participant was allowed to carry out their own warm up routine prior to the trial's initial commencement. Once the participants were comfortable, they then performed 125 golf swings using various clubs (5 x 5-iron, 60 x 7-iron, 5 x 9-iron, 55 x driver). To aid focus and ensure safety, the participants were advised to aim all golf shots towards a red target pole, behind the enclosed golf net. All golf shots were hit at a rate of one shot every 30 seconds. Feedback from an initial pilot study showed that this was a comfortable pace to perform the golf shots.

The kinematic angle data of both left and right hip, knee and ankle joints in the sagittal, transverse and frontal planes were recorded using an 8 camera Vicon Nexus Bonita (Oxford Metrics Ltd) motion capture system operating at 250 Hz. A Vicon plug in gait lower body model was selected with 16 retro-reflective markers placed on the correct anatomical positions of the lower limbs and four on the shaft of the TaylorMade golf clubs. This allowed for correct identification of the six golf phases.

As previously mentioned, these can be identified as:

- Address. The point where the club head was in close proximity to the ball at the start of the swing and the frame before backwards movement was initiated.
- Top of Backswing. The point in which the club head reached its most lateral position, towards the intended target, before changing direction.
- Acceleration. The point where the club achieved a horizontal position 90° from address.

- Impact. The moment the club head made impact with the ball.
- Early Follow Through. The position of the club head 180⁰ opposite the acceleration phase (on the left of the participant).
- Late Follow Through. Position of the club head as it reaches its most lateral position from the intended target, before changing direction.

The first five swings of the driver and 7-iron were extracted and used as “pre-fatigue” with the last 5 swings of the study stored as “post-fatigue” for evaluation and comparison purposes. All joint angle data is stored in Degrees (°).

All axes throughout this study follow the Vicon global coordinate system naming conventions with Z = superior/inferior, X = anterior/posterior, Y = lateral/medial.

5.5.4. Statistical Analysis

The average of five pre-fatigue and five post-fatigue trials were determined for all participants and expressed as a function of the golf phases of measurement using both descriptive and inferential statistics. SEM was used to quantify the absolute consistency of the measurement (Weir, 2005). Paired t-tests were carried out to compare the differences between pre-fatigue/post-fatigue (Table 5.2) and driver/7-iron (Table 5.3) swings and their corresponding joint angles. Significance was set to $P \leq 0.05$.

All calculations were performed using Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS V 22.0), Jamovi (Version 2.4.8) and Microsoft Excel (Version 2013). Pearson correlation coefficients were used to assess relationships of all means of left and right hip, knee, ankle and pelvis axis outputs as well as the practice versus fatigue across both driver and 7-iron. Normal distribution for all variables was assessed

using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The strength of the correlation (r) was interpreted as poor (0 to 0.3), moderate (0.3 to 0.5), and strong (> 0.5) (Table 5.1).

Table 5.1: Strength of Correlation Coefficient (r)

Strength of Association	Positive	Negative
Small	0.1 to 0.3	-0.1 to -0.3
Medium	0.3 to 0.5	-0.3 to -0.5
Large	0.5 to 1.0	-0.5 to -1.0

5.6. Results

This study aims to establish if muscle fatigue that has been generated by a specific golf fatiguing protocol will influence proprioception and kinematic parameters of both left and right hip knee and ankle joints. A pre versus post-fatigue t-test has displayed some significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in a number of elements throughout the study with the exception of the right knee ($(X = 0.44 \pm 0.30)$, $(Y = 0.48 \pm 0.22)$, $(Z = 0.43 \pm 0.21)$), right ankle ($(X = 0.56 \pm 0.32)$, $(Y = 0.30 \pm 0.15)$, $(Z = 0.36 \pm 0.14)$) and left hip angles ($(X = 0.23 \pm 0.23)$, $(Y = 0.43 \pm 0.29)$, $(Z = 0.34 \pm 0.19)$) during all phases.

There were also no significant differences noticed in both driver (0.33 ± 0.26) and 7-iron (0.45 ± 0.30) during the address phase, the driver at the late follow through phase (0.26 ± 0.16) and impact phases (0.30 ± 0.20) for all joint angles (Appendix 10). However, a driver versus 7-iron t-test displayed almost twice as many significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in several elements throughout the study with the exception of the left ankle angles ($(X = 0.61 \pm 0.25)$, $(Y = 0.47 \pm 0.35)$, $(Z = 0.50 \pm 0.30)$). During all phases only practice swings at the top of backswing (0.29 ± 0.20)

and late follow through phases (0.41 ± 0.24) contained no significant differences. (Appendix 10).

The left hip "X" axis (0.25 ± 0.26) has shown the most significant differences, all of which have been observed within the fatigued state. These differences can also be noted in the means and SEM graphs below: Address Phase (Figure 5.2), Top of Backswing (Figure 5.3), Acceleration (Figure 5.4), Impact (Figure 5.5), and Early Follow Through (Figure 5.6). All other data from the t-tests can be found in Appendix 10.

Figure 5.2: *Fatigued Address Phase*

Figure 5.3: *Fatigued Acceleration Phase*

Figure 5.4: *Fatigued Top of Backswing Phase*

Figure 5.5: *Fatigued Impact Phase*

Figure 5.6: *Fatigued Early Follow Through Phase*

The standard error of the mean has been calculated for all clubs, joint angles and phases (Table 5.4). The table below shows that joint angles on the left ankle ($Z = 5.31 \pm 3.81$), left hip ($Z = 5.05 \pm 5.88$), left knee ($Z = 6.62 \pm 5.79$) and right Hip ($Z = 10.92 \pm 5.07$) display a higher dispersion for the general population. This trend can also be seen individually during the driver practice of the right ankle ($Y = 11.49$), during the top of backswing phase of the left hip ($X = 14.45$) and ($Y = 10.84$) axis, as well as the left hip ($Y = 12.51$) during the impact phase. It can also be noted that with the exception of the “Z” Axis on the right hip, All SEM results greater than 10 have been shown in the practice phases. As an aside, it can be seen that all other SEM data has shown a smaller value which suggests the sample is representative of the general population.

Table 5.2: SEM of all Joint Angles and Phases

Phase	Club/Fatigue Status	LAnkX	LAnkY	LankZ	LHipX	LHipY	LHipZ	LKneeX	LKneeY	LKneeZ	RAnkX	RAnkY	RankZ	RHipX	RHipY	RHipZ	RKneeX	RKneeY	RKneeZ
Address	DR Practice	5.32	2.66	12.26	8.99	2.38	15.99	3.26	0.97	16.12	6.32	11.49	8.27	5.43	7.14	8.75	6.33	8.64	2.69
	7I Practice	1.04	0.58	2.20	2.58	1.29	1.30	1.88	0.71	1.57	1.24	0.43	1.68	7.14	8.98	22.18	2.21	0.77	2.37
	DR Fatigue	1.24	0.99	2.69	2.14	1.63	2.79	1.77	0.68	2.01	1.49	0.43	1.84	4.53	4.23	9.24	1.76	0.71	2.32
	7I Fatigue	1.14	0.76	2.50	2.58	1.19	1.97	1.85	0.79	1.87	1.41	0.55	2.09	3.18	3.75	9.73	1.94	0.79	2.37
Top of Bakswing	DR Practice	4.76	2.08	12.08	14.45	10.84	15.68	4.34	3.22	16.19	5.68	9.42	8.26	4.21	6.29	3.76	6.16	8.65	3.24
	7I Practice	1.25	0.85	2.84	2.26	2.45	1.82	2.30	0.98	2.22	1.39	0.67	2.39	3.92	8.01	17.83	1.59	0.94	2.78
	DR Fatigue	1.53	0.99	3.29	2.33	2.57	2.27	2.80	0.97	2.24	1.74	0.68	2.50	4.29	5.92	12.30	1.51	1.01	2.76
	7I Fatigue	1.12	0.72	2.68	2.72	2.55	2.00	2.74	0.90	2.24	1.14	0.70	2.65	2.80	4.50	9.41	3.21	3.11	4.04
Acceleration	DR Practice	4.27	2.99	11.94	6.96	2.07	15.09	3.42	0.63	16.01	6.88	8.13	8.51	4.02	5.31	2.88	7.35	9.19	5.24
	7I Practice	1.14	1.03	3.33	1.57	1.94	1.32	1.74	0.72	1.95	1.61	0.68	2.39	5.22	6.01	17.96	2.19	0.94	2.23
	DR Fatigue	2.62	1.14	3.52	1.60	1.34	1.34	1.80	0.77	3.42	2.02	0.63	2.17	5.57	2.26	11.64	1.91	1.10	2.24
	7I Fatigue	2.16	0.99	3.21	1.80	1.55	1.37	2.08	0.69	5.36	1.40	0.74	2.54	2.50	4.00	9.52	3.53	3.01	3.84
Impact	DR Practice	4.45	3.14	11.87	9.33	12.51	15.14	3.47	0.69	16.40	7.33	7.99	8.75	4.47	5.37	3.00	8.12	9.65	6.21
	7I Practice	1.67	1.14	3.46	1.41	2.21	1.34	1.78	0.64	2.14	1.72	0.78	2.52	5.65	5.85	18.17	2.25	1.04	2.42
	DR Fatigue	2.83	1.16	3.49	1.25	1.36	1.41	1.54	0.68	3.74	2.26	0.73	2.33	5.81	1.74	11.96	1.93	1.20	2.48
	7I Fatigue	2.02	1.20	3.49	1.52	1.78	1.52	1.83	0.72	5.75	1.57	0.85	2.72	2.71	4.04	9.80	3.50	3.10	4.00
Early follow through	DR Practice	4.43	3.16	11.64	4.12	4.64	14.91	3.40	0.82	16.57	7.68	7.86	8.95	5.02	5.33	3.15	6.47	7.92	3.57
	7I Practice	1.97	1.13	3.16	1.71	2.15	1.47	1.68	0.55	1.96	1.96	0.77	2.55	6.52	5.57	18.19	2.48	1.38	2.57
	DR Fatigue	2.93	1.10	3.31	1.21	1.43	1.51	1.36	0.63	3.94	2.54	0.71	2.33	6.37	1.37	12.09	2.06	1.36	2.71
	7I Fatigue	1.89	1.14	3.30	1.61	1.80	1.53	1.56	0.55	6.30	1.64	0.86	2.70	3.34	3.78	9.62	3.53	3.21	4.06
Late follow through	DR Practice	5.18	3.40	11.42	4.86	4.54	14.41	3.46	1.16	16.42	9.40	7.44	9.31	5.78	5.74	6.59	6.40	6.46	3.08
	7I Practice	2.15	1.24	2.87	1.64	1.74	1.58	1.06	0.74	1.61	2.80	0.73	2.40	6.10	3.77	12.84	1.96	1.27	2.81
	DR Fatigue	2.11	1.54	3.43	1.22	1.44	1.76	0.97	0.61	6.43	3.00	0.93	2.72	7.08	3.24	12.35	2.17	1.16	3.33
	7I Fatigue	2.39	1.54	3.35	1.83	1.97	1.63	1.41	0.79	6.44	2.82	0.77	2.56	5.60	2.17	9.21	3.45	3.07	4.21

Key for above Table:

	< 10
	>10

A Pearson correlation coefficient shows that when comparing the driver against the 7-iron across all club phases and joints, a small association is shown on most of the phases of the left pelvis angle (($X = 0.01 \pm 0.09$), ($Y = 0.05 \pm 0.10$), ($Z = 0.04 \pm 0.09$)) , right pelvis angle (($X = 0.03 \pm 0.13$), ($Y = 0.07 \pm 0.14$), ($Z = 0.22 \pm 0.16$)) and the right hip angle (($X = 0.00 \pm 0.12$), ($Y = 0.04 \pm 0.09$), ($Z = 0.03 \pm 0.15$)). All other phases/joint angle combination proved to show mostly medium or large associations. It can also be noted that similar results were achieved when splitting the correlation coefficient results by club and fatigue status. This was especially prevalent in the right hip angles (by club ($X = 0.05 \pm 0.12$), ($Y = 0.04 \pm 0.09$), ($Z = 0.01 \pm 0.07$)) (Table 5.3), (by fatigue status ($X = 0.04 \pm 0.13$), ($Y = 0.03 \pm 0.09$), ($Z = 0.06 \pm 0.07$)) see (Table 5.4). It has also been highlighted that better correlation can be seen during all fatigued figures whilst measuring by club and also the 7-iron when measuring by fatigue status.

A key for each of the two correlation tables can be seen below.

Key for Correlation Tables (5.3 and 5.4)

Key	
0 to 0.3 and -0 to -0.3	
0.3 to 0.5 and -0.3 to -0.5	
0.5 to 1 and -0.5 to -1	

Table 5.3: Correlation Coefficient by Club

Phase	Club/Fatigue Status	LAnkX	LAnkY	LankZ	LHipX	LHipY	LHipZ	LKneeX	LKneeY	LKneeZ	LPeIX	LPeY	LPeIZ	RAnkX	RAnkY	RankZ	RHipX	RHipY	RHipZ	RKneeX	RKneeY	RKneeZ	RPeIX	RPeY	RPeIZ
Address	DR V 7I Prac	0.02	0.13	0.08	-0.16	0.08	0.07	-0.01	0.39	0.11	0.35	0.12	0.43	-0.01	0.03	0.15	-0.08	-0.08	-0.05	-0.08	-0.14	0.59	-0.41	0.43	0.02
	DR V 7I Fat	0.42	0.37	0.56	0.44	0.27	0.34	0.45	0.31	0.77	0.00	-0.04	0.15	0.21	0.67	0.72	0.11	-0.01	0.09	0.50	0.57	0.86	0.20	0.35	0.56
Top of Backswing	DR V 7I Prac	0.07	0.21	0.16	0.20	-0.15	0.19	0.20	0.14	0.13	0.04	-0.22	0.12	0.12	0.03	0.25	0.11	0.10	-0.07	-0.02	0.11	0.58	-0.08	-0.02	-0.06
	DR V 7I Fat	0.27	0.52	0.53	0.81	0.23	0.71	0.28	0.32	0.67	0.01	-0.01	0.15	0.27	0.71	0.76	0.27	-0.03	0.09	0.15	0.30	0.52	0.07	0.33	0.20
Acceleration	DR V 7I Prac	0.39	0.38	0.03	-0.25	0.24	0.09	0.24	0.59	0.44	0.03	-0.22	0.20	0.11	0.11	0.13	-0.06	0.01	-0.08	-0.05	0.17	0.35	0.06	0.03	0.10
	DR V 7I Fat	0.91	0.48	0.58	0.47	0.42	0.74	0.47	0.40	0.94	0.00	-0.03	0.06	0.50	0.74	0.68	0.08	0.14	0.06	0.22	0.34	0.50	-0.03	0.12	0.27
Impact	DR V 7I Prac	0.50	0.39	-0.03	-0.20	0.05	0.08	0.14	0.34	0.49	0.05	-0.22	0.21	0.18	0.11	0.09	-0.06	-0.01	-0.08	-0.07	0.16	0.31	0.08	-0.08	0.10
	DR V 7I Fat	0.81	0.48	0.60	0.52	0.32	0.76	0.50	0.21	0.94	0.03	-0.02	0.02	0.60	0.72	0.59	0.04	0.17	0.07	0.28	0.34	0.55	0.14	0.03	0.25
Early follow through	DR V 7I Prac	0.45	0.35	-0.07	0.01	0.15	0.06	0.07	0.16	0.45	0.08	-0.22	0.21	0.22	0.13	0.07	0.00	-0.03	-0.07	-0.03	0.16	0.62	-0.01	-0.03	0.03
	DR V 7I Fat	0.51	0.62	0.60	0.59	0.37	0.80	0.34	0.14	0.95	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.69	0.59	0.47	0.02	0.18	0.06	0.28	0.40	0.60	0.06	0.00	0.25
Late follow through	DR V 7I Prac	0.35	0.25	0.13	0.17	0.20	-0.11	0.14	0.25	0.14	0.15	-0.31	0.43	0.29	0.14	0.25	0.14	0.05	0.08	-0.01	0.14	0.76	0.07	-0.05	0.20
	DR V 7I Fat	0.69	0.64	0.45	0.57	0.50	0.62	0.49	0.67	0.98	0.01	-0.02	0.03	0.50	0.76	0.74	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.14	0.27	0.48	0.03	0.12	0.33

Table 5.4: Correlation Coefficient by Fatigue Status

Phase	Club/Fatigue Status	LAnkX	LAnkY	LankZ	LHipX	LHipY	LHipZ	LKneeX	LKneeY	LKneeZ	LPeIX	LPeY	LPeIZ	RAnkX	RAnkY	RankZ	RHipX	RHipY	RHipZ	RKneeX	RKneeY	RKneeZ	RPeIX	RPeY	RPeIZ
Address	DR Prac V Fat	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.13	0.12	0.06	0.24	0.33	0.21	-0.03	0.02	0.07	0.14	0.09	0.21	-0.02	0.10	0.03	0.14	0.25	0.80	0.12	-0.11	0.30
	7I Prac V Fat	0.39	0.52	0.66	0.44	0.24	0.58	0.21	0.36	0.67	-0.08	0.00	0.10	0.48	0.64	0.63	-0.08	-0.06	-0.03	0.38	0.59	0.74	-0.11	0.00	0.31
Top of Backswing	DR Prac V Fat	0.09	0.17	0.16	-0.06	0.09	0.17	0.19	0.15	0.03	-0.03	0.02	0.00	0.10	0.20	0.35	0.06	0.04	0.20	0.15	0.23	0.68	-0.03	0.17	0.10
	7I Prac V Fat	0.20	0.60	0.70	0.76	0.52	0.83	0.53	0.59	0.81	-0.09	-0.03	-0.03	0.38	0.62	0.62	-0.20	0.22	-0.03	0.16	0.22	0.51	-0.03	0.15	0.44
Acceleration	DR Prac V Fat	0.14	0.12	0.19	0.01	0.21	0.10	0.15	0.65	0.06	-0.02	-0.01	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.17	-0.05	0.10	0.12	0.04	0.28	0.40	0.02	-0.08	-0.05
	7I Prac V Fat	0.29	0.37	0.47	0.48	0.04	0.73	0.36	0.56	0.03	-0.06	-0.03	0.07	0.43	0.43	0.42	-0.26	-0.06	-0.01	0.24	0.27	0.46	-0.03	0.07	0.35
Impact	DR Prac V Fat	0.20	0.12	0.14	-0.04	0.20	0.09	0.13	0.40	0.08	-0.03	-0.01	0.05	0.11	0.08	0.14	-0.10	0.09	0.10	0.00	0.25	0.36	0.03	0.04	-0.03
	7I Prac V Fat	0.42	0.33	0.40	0.32	0.10	0.72	0.29	0.16	0.02	-0.04	-0.04	0.11	0.45	0.51	0.43	-0.09	-0.07	0.02	0.25	0.29	0.50	0.07	0.05	0.33
Early follow through	DR Prac V Fat	0.16	0.12	0.12	0.17	0.28	0.07	0.03	0.18	0.08	-0.02	-0.01	0.05	0.16	0.08	0.13	-0.06	0.11	0.13	0.07	0.24	0.70	-0.02	0.05	0.14
	7I Prac V Fat	0.40	0.40	0.47	0.37	0.33	0.70	0.38	0.21	0.12	-0.01	-0.04	0.14	0.42	0.63	0.55	0.10	-0.08	0.02	0.28	0.37	0.54	0.21	0.05	0.33
Late follow through	DR Prac V Fat	0.38	0.04	0.01	0.16	0.33	-0.01	0.02	0.23	0.01	-0.01	0.00	0.07	0.04	0.19	0.23	-0.05	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.21	0.63	0.01	0.12	0.35
	7I Prac V Fat	0.53	0.33	0.42	0.59	0.46	0.76	0.14	0.52	0.27	0.01	0.03	0.41	0.47	0.85	0.82	0.23	-0.03	0.02	0.08	0.33	0.53	0.22	-0.11	0.37

5.7. Discussion

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effect of fatigue on hip, knee, and ankle proprioception during a golf specific fatigue protocol.

The findings of this study have shown some significant differences with exception of the right knee and left hip angles during all phases with both driver and 7-iron and also the driver at the top of the backswing for all joint angles. There are significant differences throughout the remainder of the swing/joint angles with this increasing during the faster phases of the swing and/or with the shorter 7-iron club.

However, the small scattering of data that displays a significant difference, does highlight that this is increased during the phases of the swing with higher CHV, (acceleration, impact and early follow through) as well as also showing a similar effect with the shorter 7-iron club. Finally, significant differences have been noted in many of the fatigued results when comparing the driver against the 7-iron. This can be further addressed when comparing the joint angle data between the address and impact (club head at same position). Whilst the impact phase shows double the number of significant differences to address, the 7-iron contributes to 83.3% of these (data of the mean and SEM of all phase/club/fatigue status (Figures 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5, 5.6) data similarly compliment that of the t-tests (Appendix 10)). Significant differences have also been noted in many of the fatigued results when comparing the driver versus the 7-iron.

Standard error of the means was calculated for all club/fatigue status variables for each phase of the golf swing. Nagele (2003) points out that this is used to give an estimate of how the mean of the sample is related to the mean of the underlying population. As can be seen from the previously mentioned SEM results table, 92.4%

of the figures have displayed that the samples are mostly representative of the population. A Pearson correlation coefficient displayed small associations across the left pelvis and right hip both when comparing by club as well as fatigue status. It can be noticed however, that a stronger association can be seen during club comparisons when measuring by fatigue status.

Biomechanical analysis of a golf swing is widely known as being difficult to interpret due to the complexity of the swing, as it has a 3D motion, multi-planar sequence, which is performed at very high speeds. The analysis benefitted from the reliability statistical measurements i.e., the ICC and CCA analysis producing reliability results comparable to the clinical study done by Sorbie et al. (2017). Future studies may choose to include other relative variables inc CHV and swing time.

5.8. Conclusions

The significant differences shown within the t-tests of the club/fatigue status comparisons have been predominantly found within the faster phases of the swing and/or with the shorter 7-iron club. This is comparable to findings in the study by Egret (2006) who points out that due to reduced hip and shoulder flexibility men flexed their left knee more at the top of the backswing to increase the arc of the swing at that point. Whilst comparing the t-test by club only, it can be seen that almost all significant differences can be found within the fatigued status. The kinematic mean data also displays a greater output in almost all clubs and phases during the fatigued state in the “Y” axis of the right ankle, knee and hip (with the exception of the driver at the top of the backswing). This data may concur and highlight the findings of Ochsendorf et al. (2000) who indicated that postural sway was increased by isokinetic fatigue of the ankle plantar flexors and dorsiflexors.

The current protocols and technology within this study have shown both excellent reproducibility and reliability. The t-test displayed a small number of significant differences, the SEM shows that the means are close to the population, and although the Pearson correlation displayed some weak medium and strong associations, it has also highlighted some other points that may be studied in the future to investigate the patterns within the data and their possible link to golf swings.

5.9. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank staff at the University of the West of Scotland for their support throughout the study and the participants for their patience and professionalism. The staff at Vicon are also acknowledged for their technical input.

6. Overall Discussion

As previously mentioned, this thesis is part of a larger, almost whole body, principal study which encompasses a number of studies by authors that utilise the Institute for Clinical Exercise & Health Science, University of the West of Scotland's biomechanical facilities. The study was designed to ascertain the suitability of current university technologies within a golf environment, design and validate golf related protocols and investigate issues that may help improve the performance of a golfer or decrease their risk of injury. Initial studies were conducted using only EMG to formulate and evaluate the protocols necessary to provide a reliable test procedure that could be brought forward into further studies within the overall group project. Figure 6.1 highlights the flow of each study throughout the project and how critical protocols, technologies and resources have been shared. These studies have utilised the Myon 320 EMG system, various 2D motion capture software systems, the Vicon Bonita motion analysis system or a combination of each technology.

Figure 6.1: Flow Diagram of Principal Project

The initial aims of this thesis were to investigate the validation of three main computer assisted systems that can be attributed to golf performance and injury prevention of the wrist, elbow, hip, knee and ankle. After significant research of literature, the final objectives of the thesis have been conceived:

- To assess the reliability of the Myon 320 EMG system during an individual, static multi-planar maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) hand grip task
- To assess the reliability of a multiple 2D low-cost augmented video-based portable systems (AVPS) (Kinovea, Siliconcoach Pro, Siliconcoach Live) against the gold standard Vicon Nexus system to compare swing time and golf club angle parameters during golf swings.
- To assess the effect that fatigue may have on each individuals' movement by using the Vicon Bonita system to collect, analyse and evaluate kinematic data of multiple participants golf swings.

The main findings of the first study within this thesis have clearly shown that when using the Myon 320 EMG system with AMBU electrodes, no significant difference has been observed in EMG output across either the FDS or ECRB when comparing the same muscle on both left and right side during different wrist positions. As hypothesised, there are significant differences when comparing both muscles on the same arm.

This study can conclude that all participants' retrieved data has been validated, and the protocols, methods and systems could be used in future trials. Whilst the study has produced good to fair reliability across the descriptive statistical outputs, further analysis and justification could be included with the implementation of collected MVC force data.

Future directions from our laboratory may include investigations on understanding the coupling of wrist movement and how these movements impact on the synergistic co-contractions of the flexor and extensor muscles during both static and dynamic related activities involving the wrist and fingers. Future trials may benefit from the inclusion of an upgraded custom splint or goniometer to ensure the exact wrist movement as well as facilitating the wrist positioning of participants who find difficulty in maintaining required positions. Previous studies have utilised many of the protocols included within this study, however, there are no precise testing guidelines available, thus making comparisons difficult.

The findings of the second study suggest that all three AVPS can be used to effectively calculate club angle parameters and swing time. The results agree with the swing time hypothesis and with the club angle output hypothesis for the golf phase measurements.

Although the study involved 'novice' participants, a large proportion of the acceleration golf phase measurements fell slightly under the 90° inclination angle measurement. The results revealed no significant differences between the 2D commercial software and 3D Vicon motion system software. The R values for the pro vs live at address, indeed were lower than the other comparisons, however the output interpretation was considered moderate. The variations between the trials for the Pro and Live were not as close as the other commercial software and Vicon Nexus software package comparisons. This is acknowledged by the size of the standard deviation.

These differences we feel may be attributed to the resolution of the software or display resolution during the manual data processing using the software tools. The ratio of the swing time for the backswing and swing time for the downswing was 2:1.

The swing time duration marginally varied across the different software because the frames representative of the phases varied by a frame or two across the various software packages. This means that identical frame numbers from one software were not replicated across the four software packages. Instead, each time a new software package was opened the frames at the start and end of the swings were inspected via effective visual examination of the video frames. Indeed, this is an important point as all raters reviewed each of the software independently by not taking previous recorded readings into consideration during the data processing stages of the outputs. Furthermore, the inter-rater reliability study provided a better approach to evaluate the utility and accuracy of the tools presented.

In general, all temporal and kinematic golf phase measurements with respect to the 3D Vicon Motion System and the 2D commercial software mean revealed no proportional bias and good agreement in the results.

To date, this is the first study that has used multiple low cost 2D AVPS to evaluate and compare the club angle parameters and the swing time of a golf swing. While there are no recent studies that show 2D motion analysis for a golf swing, (Wright, 2008) provides a detailed historical perspective and description of motion capture technologies and methodologies that have influenced golf biomechanics, club fitting, coaching and golf instruction.

As a limitation, the sample size was small; however, this study has proven that the AVPS can produce a reliable and valid output with little financial and time overheads. Unfortunately, performance variables such as CHV, ball speed, ball position relative to stance width, wrist angle at various phases of the golf swing, club path, launch angle were not incorporated as outcome measures in this research study.

These missing components were not measured as the protocol for both the 3D motion system and AVPS did not include a marker on the golf club head. Also due to the high speed of the ball post impact, the ball position, ball pathway and ball distance could not be clearly determined and thus would have affected the level of accuracy needed to extract the desired performance outputs.

Studies are underway that involve higher shutter speeds. This will prevent streaking and make the digitisation of the markers more reliable. Furthermore, to calculate these performance variables, during the experiment validation process, three independent systems would have had to be used namely a Voice Caddie Swing Launch Monitor (or Trackman™ III Golf Swing) together with a 2D high speed video camera and 3D motion system. The analyses benefitted from the reliability statistical measurements i.e., the ICC and CCA analysis producing reliability results comparable to the clinical study done by Ugbolue et al. (2013). Future studies may choose to use only amateur golfers or perhaps professional golfers with a low handicap.

Finally, the use of 2D AVPS software packages should be encouraged among movement analysis researchers and coaches, particularly when 3D motion capture systems and software cannot be accessed.

The findings of the third and final study has shown a number of significant differences throughout when comparing the driver versus the 7-iron and practice versus fatigue. Whilst some joint or club/fatigue status variables contain little or no significant differences, it can be noted that most can be seen with the 7-iron (when comparing fatigue status) and when fatigued (during club comparison). These

significant differences can also be seen during all comparisons mainly during the fast phases of the golf swing.

The kinematic mean data has displayed a greater output in almost all clubs and phases during the fatigued state in the “Y” axis of the right ankle, knee and hip (with the exception of the driver at the top of the backswing). This data may concur and highlight the findings of Ochsendorf et al. (2000) who indicated that postural sway was increased by isokinetic fatigue of the ankle plantar flexors and dorsiflexors.

This study also can conclude that all retrieved data, protocols, methods and systems are valid and can be effectively used in future trials. The study has produced good to fair reliability across the descriptive statistical outputs. However, further analysis and justification could be included to further research patterns within the coefficient data to link with previous kinematic findings. It may also be beneficial in future studies to use low handicapped/professional players as this may reduce some of the variability found within current data and give an even clearer view of reliability.

6.1. Contributions to the Literature

This thesis has uncovered several positive contributions to previous literature. Study One has identified the requirement for, and created, a working prototype elbow placement rig to prevent other biomechanical movements of any part of the body to cause a distortion of forearm muscle activation levels. The usage of this rig and test protocol has allowed for reliable testing of surface EMG signals from both the flexor digitorum superficialis and extensor carpi radialis brevis muscles of both left and right arms during an individual, static multi-planar maximum voluntary contraction handgrip task when using the Myon 320 system (Myon AG, Switzerland).

Study Two similarly has provided positive contributions to both 2D video analysis as

well as golf literature. This study has provided a reassuring output for both sport coaches, academics, and clinicians alike who are examining the usages of 2D AVPS within their current environments. Study Three has added to the limited research of muscular fatigue during golf within a lower limb kinematic setting.

These positive contributions around the areas of the hip, knee and ankle also may be utilised out with a golf environment, especially where fatigue may be perceived as a contributing factor to poor movement or injury whilst participating in the sport.

6.2. Overview of Limitations

The researchers acknowledge that there are a few limitations within the studies of this thesis. Firstly, throughout all studies, each has a limited number of participants. An increase in these numbers may strengthen the findings of the studies. Each of the trials were performed within a laboratory environment. Whilst this will possibly have had no effect during the handgrip study, there are thoughts that especially with the golf fatigue protocols, figures may be different if a more realistic golf course protocol could be implemented. The timing gap between shots in a normal round of golf would be significantly increased. There may also be further fatigue when walking from the taken shot area to the ball in preparation for the next shot. There is also the possibility of further fatigue being introduced because of continual lifting and carrying the golf bag, clubs and any other required equipment.

Almost all participants within this study were novice golfers. An even mix of amateur and professional golfers would have given the researchers the ability to investigate any differences in movement during fatigue between both test groups.

All golf studies within this thesis did not investigate club head speed. This may have been useful to further evaluate a number of golf related issues (especially around

fatigue). Lastly, the age and general fitness of participants was also beyond the scope of the golf fatigue study. It may be deemed feasible that by utilising both variables, the researchers may be able to find a causative explanation to some of the fatigued data.

6.3. Recommendations for Future Research

By increasing the scope of the golf swing studies to consider muscle fatigue, club head speed and even ball speed may allow future researchers to further identify patterns within the data that may give greater cause behind the effects that have been acknowledged within this thesis. Furthermore, the inclusion of lifting, walking and carrying of clubs (or emulation of such) to replicate a physical round of golf may also be included in future studies.

Initially, one other study had been planned to complete this overall project. Kinetic analysis of a golf swing during pre and post fatigue golf swings would provide a view of the lower limb forces produced during a golf fatiguing protocol. This further study may provide an insight into the kinematic results of the fatigue effect on golf swing phase movements. All testing and collection of data is currently complete. This final study shall be ready for publishing following the successful completion of this thesis.

Focus has been drawn towards individual areas or muscle groups during each study. It may also be feasible to increase the number of retro reflective balls and EMG sensor to encapsulate significantly more parts of the body and provide a more holistic study that looks at both upper and lower body movement simultaneously. Again, there may be links to movement changes that originate from elsewhere that are currently not being investigated.

Finally, the author would like to take some of these protocols and utilise them within an alternative sporting environment (with similar movement patterns). The athletics sport of hammer throwing contains many of the same features but in a more three-dimensional movement. This sport is a low volume participant sport therefore research into this area is significantly less than that of golf. In turn, the contribution to current literature would be significantly greater.

6.4. Conclusions

This thesis has provided further underpinning knowledge of muscular activity from both left and right ECRB and FDS during multiple wrist positions. The study has provided clear, reliable guidelines regarding the setup of the test procedure to ensure that future researchers can confidently recreate the same tests with no increase/decrease in muscle output due to participant movement and recruitment of other muscles. Other investigations have concluded that a low cost 2D AVPS can be used in the absence of the significantly more expensive and larger gold standard 3D motion capture system.

Finally, this thesis is the first to use the Vicon Bonita system to record lower limb movement during a fatigue inducing golf swing protocol. This can be seen as a valuable tool that can be used to possibly improve performance or indeed reduce injury risk whilst participating in the game of golf. The findings of the studies within this thesis have already spawned a variety of other works that have researched similar muscle activation or body movements, used the same protocols during tests or indeed integrated the same uniformed technical equipment.

In conjunction with other previous authors' works, this thesis also agrees that 2D AVPS, 3D motion capture and surface EMG has the flexibility to be used to have a better understanding of specific muscle activity and body movement during the game

of golf. It also identifies that these technologies can be used in both a clinical environment to ultimately reduce the risk of injury during a game of golf but also in a sporting context to improve the performance of a golfer.

7. References

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8. Appendices

8.1. Appendix 1

Participation Information Form

Research Title:

RELIABILITY OF FOREARM MUSCLE ELECTROMYOGRAPHY DATA DURING MULTI-PLANAR MAXIMUM VOLUNTARY CONTRACTION GRIP AND WRIST ARTICULATION

Introduction:

You are being invited to participate in a research study. This form will provide you with the information of what the research involves. Please read the following information carefully and if you have any questions do not hesitate to contact me (contact details can be found at the foot of this form).

Thank you for regarding this.

Who I am and the purpose of the Study:

My name is Henry Hunter and I am currently a Lecturer and PhD student at the University of The West of Scotland. I also have qualifications in coaching Football, Swimming and Athletics. As part of my PhD project, I am going to investigate muscular signal during hand grip protocol.

Why have I been chosen?

Your age and health status makes you eligible for selection.

What will I be required to do if I take part?

You will be asked to sit on chair and place your arm at right angles at the elbow in a rig to maintain stability and perform a number of maximum hand grip contractions.

Do I Have to Take Part?

If you would be interested in taking part in the study I would be grateful if you could contact me within 1 week after receiving this form.

You will also be asked to sign a consent form. This form will give you the opportunity to withdraw at any stage and no reason for withdrawal is needed.

The Benefits of Taking Part:

The study participants will leave the study with valuable experience. They will be exposed to using high spec motion analysis and muscle activity equipment which will provide useful benefits of using the correct grip size.

Will my involvement in this study be kept Confidential?

All data from PAR-Qs, consent forms and feedback sheets will be placed in a password protected electronic computer and forms will be kept in a locked filing cabinet in the University of The West of Scotland. Also graphs and tables for the data analysis will be recorded as participant 1, participant 2 and so forth. Participants can locate their data on request to identify their own recordings.

Who will have access to this information?

Only the researcher and supervisor will have access to passwords for the electronic computer. Any Par Qs, feedback and consent forms will be filed in the supervisor's locked filing cabinet. This can only be accessed by the supervisor themselves.

For any further information on this study please do not hesitate to contact myself on the following details.

Contact Information

Researcher: Henry Hunter

University of the West of Scotland

Ayr Campus

University Avenue

Ayr

KA8 0SX

Email address: [REDACTED]

Contact number: [REDACTED]

8.2. Appendix 2

PAR-Q FORM

Regular physical activity is fun and healthy, and an increasing number of people are starting to become more active every day. Golf, being a form of physical activity is very safe for most people. However, some people should complete a series of questions before partaking in physical activity. ***Please complete this form as accurately and completely as possible.***

PAR-Q FORM Please mark YES or NO to the following: Yes

No

Has your doctor ever said that you have a heart condition and recommended only medically supervised physical activity?	—	—
Do you frequently have chest pains when you perform physical activity?	—	—
In the past month, have you had chest pain when you were not doing physical activity?	—	—
Have you had a stroke?	—	—
Do you lose your balance due to dizziness or do you ever lose consciousness?	—	—
<u>Golf Related Questions</u>	—	—
Have you had any surgery over the past 5 years?	—	—

If you have marked YES to any of the above, please elaborate below:

Please note: if your health changes such that you could answer YES to any of the above questions, inform the researcher immediately. Ask whether you should continue with the study.

I have read, understood, and completed the questionnaire. Any questions I had were answered to my full satisfaction.

Print Name: _____ Signature:

Date: _____

8.3. Appendix 3

Participation Information Form

Research Title:

Golf Swing Analysis: Fatigue Evaluation at the Hip, Knee and Ankle Using Kinematics, Kinetic and COP Outcome Measures

Introduction:

You are being invited to participate in a research study. This form will provide you with the information of what the research involves. Please read the following information carefully and if you have any questions do not hesitate to contact me (contact details can be found at the foot of this form).

Thank you for regarding this.

Who I am and the purpose of the Study:

My name is Henry Hunter and I am currently a Lecturer and PhD student at the University of The West of Scotland. I also have qualifications in coaching Football, Swimming and Athletics. As part of my PhD project I am going to investigate how fatigue can have an effect on movement and performance from a biomechanical and physiological perspective.

Why have I been chosen?

Your golf background and handicap (+5-5) (10-25) has made you eligible to take part in the experiment.

What will I be required to do if I take part?

Participants will be required to take part in one testing session. Retro reflective markers will be placed on your hips, knees, ankles and feet. You will have to warm-up appropriately for 5 minutes before conducting 125 golf shots in total (5-iron, 7-iron, 9-iron and driver). The testing will last for approximately 2 hours.

Do I Have to Take Part?

If you would be interested in taking part in the study I would be grateful if you could contact me within 1 week after receiving this form.

You will also be asked to sign a consent form. This form will give you the opportunity to withdraw at any stage and no reason for withdrawal is needed.

The Benefits of Taking Part:

The study participants will leave the study with valuable experience. They will be exposed to using high spec motion analysis and muscle activity equipment which will provide useful benefits of using the correct grip size.

Will my involvement in this study be kept Confidential?

All data from PAR-Qs, consent forms and feedback sheets will be placed in a password protected electronic computer and forms will be kept in a locked filing cabinet in the University of The West of Scotland. Also graphs and tables for the data analysis will be recorded as participant 1, participant 2 and so forth. Participants can locate their data on request to identify their own recordings.

Who will have access to this information?

Only the researcher and supervisor will have access to passwords for the electronic computer. Any Par Qs, feedback and consent forms will be filed in the supervisor's locked filing cabinet. This can only be accessed by the supervisor themselves.

For any further information on this study please do not hesitate to contact myself on the following details.

Contact Information

Researcher: Henry Hunter

University of the West of Scotland

Ayr Campus

University Avenue

Ayr

KA8 0SX

Email address: [REDACTED]

Contact number: [REDACTED]

8.4. Appendix 4

Golf Protocol Sheet

Copy of Protocol

This study will be carried out at the University of the West of Scotland, Hamilton campus, where participants data will be collected at the Biomechanics Laboratory, located in room A074. The set up for this study consists of a golf mat, club, plastic balls and an indoor golf net. A video camera will be placed in line with the golf mat, which will record the 2D analysis, while 8 cameras around the lab are arranged for 3D analysis recording.

Upon entering the lab participants will be asked to fill out a Par-Q form and sign a copy of the consent form (which can be seen at the end of this document). Measurements will then be taken of the participants' age, height and weight. Bulls-eye markers can then be placed on the frontal plane of the body, where 6 markers will be placed on each ankle, knee and hips. These bulls-eye markers are essential, as they will show up on the 3D and 2D motion analysis screens. Once markers are in place, participants will then be asked to stand on the golf mat in front of the video camera and perform 3 golf swings. After these 3 golf swings have been performed markers can be removed and data collection from the participant is complete.

8.5. Appendix 5

Consent Form

Research Title: Golf Swing Analysis: Fatigue Evaluation at the Hip, Knee and Ankle Using Kinematics, Kinetic and COP Outcome Measures.

In completing the consent form, I agree that I, (PRINT NAME)
understand that:

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

(Insert Initials)

2. My Participation in this study is voluntary there for I may wish to withdraw at any stage with no explanation needed.

(Insert initials)

3. There is a potential risk of injury by taking part in the study. This risk is due to you having to perform golf swings and striking the golf ball.

(Insert initials)

4. I agree to take part in this study.

(Insert Initials)

Participant's Name: _____

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Researcher's Name: _____

Researcher's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Contact Information:

Researcher: Henry Hunter

University of the West of Scotland

Ayr Campus

University Avenue

Ayr

KA8 0SX

Email address: [REDACTED]

Contact number: [REDACTED]

8.6. Appendix 6

Consent Form

Research Title: Reliability of Forearm Muscle Electromyography Data During Multi-Planar Maximum Voluntary Contraction Grip and Wrist Articulation.

In completing the consent form, I agree that I, (PRINT NAME)
understand that:

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

(Insert Initials)

2. My Participation in this study is voluntary there for I may wish to withdraw at any stage with no explanation needed.

(Insert initials)

3. There is a potential risk of injury by taking part in the study. This risk is due to you having to perform golf swings and striking the golf ball.

(Insert initials)

4. I agree to take part in this study.

(Insert Initials)

Participant's Name: _____

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Researcher's Name: _____

Researcher's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Contact Information:

Researcher: Henry Hunter

University of the West of Scotland

Ayr Campus

University Avenue

Ayr

KA8 0SX

Email address: [REDACTED]

Contact number: [REDACTED]

8.7. Appendix 7

Vicon Recommended Marker Placement.

Pelvis

LASI	Left ASIS	Placed directly over the left anterior superior iliac spine
RASI	Right ASIS	Placed directly over the right anterior superior iliac spine
<p>The above markers may need to be placed medially to the ASIS to ensure the marker is in the correct position due to the curvature of the abdomen. In some participants, especially those who are obese, the markers either can't be placed exactly anterior to the ASIS, or may be invisible in this position to cameras. In these cases, each marker should be moved laterally by an equal amount, along the ASIS-ASIS axis. The true inter-ASIS Distance must then be recorded and entered on the participant parameters form. These markers, together with the sacral marker or LPSI and RPSI markers, define the pelvic axes.</p>		
LPSI	Left PSIS	Placed directly over the left posterior superior iliac spine
RPSI	Right PSIS	Placed directly over the right posterior superior iliac spine
<p>LPSI and RPSI markers are placed on the slight bony prominences that can be located immediately below the dimples (sacro-iliac joints), at the point where the spine joins the pelvis.</p>		

Leg Markers

LKNE	Left knee	Placed on the lateral epicondyle of the left knee
<p>To locate the "precise" point for the knee marker placement, passively flex and extend the knee a little while watching the skin surface on the lateral aspect of the knee joint. Identify where knee joint axis passes through the lateral side of the knee by finding the lateral skin surface that comes closest to remaining fixed in the thigh. This landmark should also be the point about which the lower leg appears to rotate. Mark this point with a pen. With a participant standing, this pen mark should be about 1.5 cm above the joint line, mid-way between the front and back of the joint. Attach the marker at this point.</p>		
LTHI	Left thigh	Place the marker over the lower lateral 1/3 surface of the thigh (Vastus Lateralis), just below the swing of the hand, although the height is not critical.
<p>The thigh markers are used to calculate the knee flexion axis location and orientation. Place the marker over the lower lateral 1/3 surface of the thigh, just below the swing of the hand, although the height is not critical. The antero-posterior placement of the marker is critical for correct alignment of the knee flexion axis. Try to keep the thigh marker off the belly of the muscle (Vastus Lateralis), but place the thigh marker at least two marker diameters proximal of the knee marker. Adjust the position of the marker so that it is aligned in the plane that contains the hip and knee joint centres and the knee flexion/extension axis. There is also another method that uses a mirror to align this marker, allowing the operator to better judge the positioning.</p>		
LANK	Left ankle	Placed on the lateral malleolus along an imaginary line that

		passes through the transmalleolar axis
LTIB	Left tibial	wand marker Similar to the thigh markers, these are placed over the lower 1/3 of the shank to determine the alignment of the ankle flexion axis
<p>The tibial marker should lie in the plane that contains the knee and ankle joint centres and the ankle flexion/extension axis. In a normal participant the ankle joint axis, between the medial and lateral malleoli, is externally rotated by between 5 and 15 degrees with respect to the knee flexion axis. The placements of the shank markers should reflect this.</p>		

Foot Markers

LTOE	Left toe	Placed over the second metatarsal head, on the mid-foot side of the equinus break between fore-foot and mid-foot
LHEE	Left heel	Placed on the calcaneus at the same height above the plantar surface of the foot as the toe marker

8.8. Appendix 8

Ethical Approval Form

University Ethics Committee

APPLICATION FORM FOR ETHICAL APPROVAL (UEC1)

N.B. The UEC Guidelines for Ethical Research with Human Subjects must be read prior to the completion of this form. Notes for each section of the application are provided under Section 2 (pp 11-12) of the Guidelines.

1	Name of principal investigator	Graeme Sorbie, Henry Hunter
	School/Address	Sport, Health and Exercise School of Science, Hamilton Campus
	Position	PhD Students
2	Name of supervisor/director of studies (for undergraduate/postgraduate applications only)	Dr. UC Ugbolue
	School/Address	Sport, Health and Exercise School of Science, Hamilton Campus
	Position	Lecturer

3	Title of Study A biomechanical and physiological evaluation of golf training aids during golf swing and golf putting.
---	--

4	What is the primary purpose of this study?	
	Original research	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Audit	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Undergraduate dissertation	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Postgraduate dissertation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Other (please detail)	<input type="checkbox"/>

5	Has the proposed study been submitted to any other ethics committee?	
	Has approval been given?	
	No	

6	What is the justification for the research? What is the background? Why is this an area of importance?	
	<p>The overall goal of this investigation is to evaluate three golf training aids by determining what effect they can have on golf related injuries and changing the biomechanics of the golf swing. Two training aids will be targeting the golf swing and one will be focused on putting. Kinetic and kinematic analysis will be incorporated into the study. Kinetic analysis will be conducted with the use of force plates, testing the weight transfer of the golfer throughout the golf swing. Motion analysis will be used to capture joint angles of the elbow and wrist at the end of the backswing and with the wrist movement in the putting test.</p>	
	<p>Electromyography readings from the flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS), the flexor carpi ulnaris (FCU), and the flexor pollicis longus (FPL), forearm muscles and ultrasound will be conducted to investigate the impact the golf swing has on hand, wrist, elbow and spinal injuries. This will be tested with the use of three different grip size on the golf club (undersize, standard and oversize).</p>	
	<p>Justification of the study:</p> <p>Over the past decade there has been a huge increase in golf research regarding injuries. This research is often focused on the biomechanical characteristics of the golf swing, physical conditioning and equipment all in relation to injury (<u>McCarroll, 1996</u>, <u>Thériault and Lachance, 1998</u>, <u>Fradkin et al., 2005</u>, <u>Grimshaw et al., 2002</u>, <u>Batt, 1992</u>). The majority of this research on golf injuries generally focuses on the skill differentiation of the golfer (<u>Batt, 1992</u>, <u>Vad et al., 2004</u>, <u>McHardy et al., 2007</u>).</p> <p>Golf is distinctive from many other sports because it can be played by young and old, and by males and females often from different backgrounds (Stockard, 2001, Thériault and Lachance, 1998, Gosheger et al., 2003) Golf is normally not considered as a strenuous sport due to the minimal aerobic effort required during practice and</p>	

competition (Stockard, 2001, Batt, 1992), therefore it is considered a low risk in relation to injury (Thériault and Lachance, 1998). Nevertheless, professional and amateur golfers can sustain significant injuries that tend to be similar, and with the popularity of the sport increasing, the rate of reported injuries can be expected to rise (Batt, 1992). Sports that involved striking tasks tend to require significant neuromuscular coordination between lower and upper extremities (Kainberger, 2007) particularly the golf swing. Vlad et al. (2004) reports the modern golf swing is suspected of being a major contributor to the increasing levels of injury in golf. This is due to the twisting motion in the lumbar spine in the backswing the hyperextension during the downswing and the wrist angle during the decent of the golf swing and on impact (Vad et al., 2004, Gluck et al., 2008, Fedorcik et al., 2012).

The most frequent injuries that often occur amongst golfers are back (spine), hand, wrist and elbow injuries (Fedorcik et al., 2012, McHardy and Pollard, 2004). Several studies have evaluated kinematics of the golf swing within a varied skill range in relation to injury (Batt, 1992, Thériault and Lachance, 1998, Vad et al., 2004). Within professional golfers these injuries are often due to overuse of the joints and muscles, whereas amateur golfers tend to sustain muscle injuries because of the biomechanical characteristics of their golf swing. Traumatic injuries can also occur, resulting from hitting the turf or a tree root (McHardy and Pollard, 2004).

Lower back pain (LBP) is extremely common amongst golfers that have a poor shift in weight when striking the ball (Batt, 1992). Throughout the golf swing the lumbar spine is exposed to significant axial twisting, compression and lateral bending (Hosea et al., 1990, Gluck et al., 2008). During the backswing the left external oblique muscle is responsible for the initial twisting at the trunk, at this stage (Gluck et al., 2008). From the top of the backswing to ball contact, peak muscle activity is placed in the spinal cord (Grimshaw et al., 2002), from this stage the right and left paraspinal muscles should fire simultaneously. However, golfers with LBP and golfers that display poor weight transference find it difficult to exhibit these movements (Okuda et al., 2010). A fast back swing can bring the club past parallel at the top of the swing, shifting weight to the left hand side, at this stage the spinal cord must make a large adjustment to get the club back on the correct swing plane (Do and Jaffe, 2010). During the downswing the golfer must transfer their weight from the right foot to their left foot (in a right-handed golfer) to maintain maximum power and accuracy, if this does not occur it puts severe lateral flexion stress on the cervical, thoracic and lumbar spine which can promote LBP and spinal injury (Do and Jaffe, 2010). Training aids specific to transferring the body weight during the swing, which is said to promote correct swing mechanics, could have a significant effect on LPB by distributing weight more sufficiently and not entirely on the lumbar spine.

Regarding hand, wrist and elbow injuries, Fedorcik et al. (2012) report that skilled golfers tend to find the injury occurring in the lead arm (left arm for right-handed golfers), this could be related to changes in wrist kinematics between golfers of different skill levels. Hand, wrist and elbow activity is significant during the golf swing, especially on the downswing where club head speed can reach 160 km/h (Thériault and Lachance, 1998). During the golf swing the wrist often exceeds its maximal functional capacity, especially in the downswing and striking of the ball, which can cause overuse stress or increase the chances of a traumatic injury. At the peak of the swing the wrist angle can often be overly extended, promoting stress on the wrist and making the mechanics of the rest of the swing improper (Fedorcik et al., 2012). Therefore, the phase of striking the ball, wrist and elbow injuries are at the greatest risk

due to forceful gripping while flexing and extending the joints.

With regards to wrist injuries during golf putting McHardy and Pollard (2004) report that depending on the golfers set up, particularly in the gripping of the putter, golfers can endure wrist pain or mild discomfort. The researchers reported that strengthening the right hand, which produces the hand to be in a supination position, was the main source of the wrist pain and discomfort. Research also suggests spinal posture during putting, especially in practice, can have an effect on back pain.

Thériault and Lachance (1998) report that lateral and medial epicondylitis as well as wrist injuries can occur if the hands grip the golf club too firmly or if the wrist action is too brisk. Forceful gripping of the golf club can either be due to poor swing mechanics or improper equipment. Incorrect grip size can have a major effect on forceful gripping which will have an effect of performance and risk of injury. With regards to grip size, there are 4 main sizes; undersize, standard, midsize and jumbo. Golfers generally play with the grips the manufacturers provide with the club, which are normally a standard size.

Gaps within research:

Research within the field of golf has been expanding at an incredible rate over the past decade, with the main focus of training to improve performance and injury prevention. Focusing on injury prevention many studies have looked towards physical conditioning to prevent the most common injuries in golf (Thériault and Lachance, 1998). Conditioning includes a 10-15 warm-up routine, involving sport-specific stretches to target the muscles that are significantly active throughout the golf swing. Although conditioning is very important to reduce the rate of injuries in golf, technical skill has been identified to significantly reduce the rate of injury (Fedorcik et al., 2012). Thériault and Lachance, (1998) suggest corrective technical skill can be achieved by reading material on proper swing mechanics or by visualization and modelling the golf swing on a professional golfer's swing. While these options are credible some golfers may find these tasks difficult to perform especially modelling a swing of a professional. Very rarely will you see two golf professionals with the same swing, their swings are designed for their own personal needs and development meaning it might not be beneficial for an amateur to try and interpret a professional's golf swing. It can be often difficult to change the biomechanics of the golf swing without the influence of a golf lesson or a training device. Several training aids available for amateur and professional golfers which focus on performance enhancement through changing the biomechanics of the individual's golf swing. However, these training devices are only tested by the manufacturer and have no published research to coincide with the manufacturers' outcome. It could be said training aids could have an effect on injury prevention due to them correcting the swing technique of the golfer.

Regarding injuries during golf putting, the research is very limited in this area. McHardy and Pollard (2004) reported incorrect wrist posture during the putting stroke can have a detrimental effect on wrist strain or injury. Hurrion (2009) investigated weight distribution and kinematic parameters during the putting stroke but injury was not discussed in this research. The limited research into golf putting and the effect it can have on injury gives the researcher a strong ground to increase the research in this area. Training aids designed specifically to reduce wrist activity and correct posture could have a sizable effect on reducing wrist activity throughout the stroke and aligning

the spine correctly. This could have an effect of reducing the rate of injury occurrence at the wrist and upper limb.

Finally, modern technology could also have an effect on injury prevention with manufacturers designing equipment according to a golfer's strength, physical capacity or limitations. This tends to look at shaft stiffness and length. But it could also be suggested grip size could play a major role. If the golfer's grip tension is not correct it can often cause wrist and elbow injuries due to forceful gripping of the club, this will also have a major effect on the performance of the golfer.

7 Give a full summary of the purpose, design and methodology of the planned research, including a brief explanation of the theoretical framework that informs it.

The main research in this study will look towards a quantitative approach. (Gratton and Jones, 2010) state that a quantitative approach in research involves measurable quantities. This theory shows that with the amount of numbers and statistics being produced in this study the quantitative approach is the only feasible option. There will be around 15 subjects taking part in this study. A quantitative approach within this research will give a basic but effective analysis of the data produced. This will be displayed on easy to read graphs and charts making it easy for subjects and fellow researchers to follow. Another advantage of a quantitative approach is it takes away biased opinions of the researcher because they are only plotting the exact data they calculated from the subjects. After the study is complete, the subjects will be given a qualitative feedback sheet to give their views on how the study was conducted; this will give the researcher valuable feedback and information when preparing to conduct other studies.

Research Design:

Each proposed subject within the study will be screened before participation with the use of a physical activity readiness questionnaire (PAR-Q) (Appendix II) to determine if it is safe for them to take part in the study. An informed written consent (Appendix III) form will also have to be obtained, before screening, from each subject before participation and data collection; this will make the subjects aware of what they are signing up for.

Subjects will be required to attend three separate testing days. On the first day of testing subjects will be tested with 3 different grip sizes. Undersize, standard and oversize. Subjects will hit 5 golf shots with each grip size. Ultrasound, Electromyography (EMG) and Motion Analysis techniques will be applied.

Specifically, the EMG and ultrasound protocol is as follows:

a) Obtain hand and wrist anthropometric measurements, participant's demographic data – gender, height, mass, age, leg length etc.

- b) Use a dynamometer and pinchometer to measure participant's maximum grip and pinch strength.
- c) Mount surface EMG on to muscles of the hand and forearm. Ensure the wrist crease is exposed and an adequate provision for the ultrasound probe is made on both the forearm and hand.
- d) Measure peak hand and forearm muscle activity at maximum voluntary contraction using EMG. Ensure wrist is in neutral position.
- e) Measure hand and forearm morphology and morphometry at maximum grip strength with ultrasound probe placed at the wrist crease region and midway between the wrist crease and elbow crease. Ensure wrist is in neutral position.
- f) Repeat (d) and (e) with wrist position in full flexion and full extension.
- g) Measure hand and forearm muscle activity with palms wide open and relaxed using EMG. Ensure wrist is in neutral position.
- h) Measure hand and forearm morphology and morphometry with palms wide open and relaxed with ultrasound probe placed at the wrist crease region and midway between the wrist crease and elbow crease. Ensure wrist is in neutral position.
- i) Repeat (g) and (h) with wrist position in full flexion and full extension.
- j) Measure hand and forearm muscle activity using undersize grip held with minimum grip strength. Ensure wrist is in neutral position.
- k) Measure hand and forearm morphology and morphometry whilst using the undersize grips held with minimum grip strength using Ultrasound with probe placed at wrist crease region and midway between wrist crease and elbow crease. Ensure wrist is in neutral position.
- l) Repeat procedure in section (j) and (k) but this time using standard and oversize grips.
- m) Repeat (l) with wrist position in full flexion and full extension.

With respect to the motion analysis protocol, a full body marker set will be adopted using retroreflective markers. Retroreflective markers will be placed on the entire spinal vertebra as well. Since the motion analysis system is interfaced with the Myon 320 EMG system, surface EMG wireless transmitters will be placed on the hand, forearm and spinal muscles. Participants will be required to place both feet on the force plate and then perform 5 golf swings using the three different grip sizes.

Recruitment strategy:

Proposed participants involved in this study will be selected based on their level of participation in golf. This research targets golfers with a wide ranging handicap of +5-36. Participant information sheet (Appendix I) will be handed to the targeted golfers; they will then have one week to confirm their participation in the study.

Data Collection Methods:

A collection of data will be taken from each subject with the use of scientific devices. First electromyography equipment will be used to measure wrist activity from 4 forearm muscles throughout the golf swing. The same device will be used to calculate muscle activity in the cervical, thoracic and lumbar sections of the spine.

Force plates will be used for kinetic analysis in the lower limbs for weight transference from the start to the completion of the golf swing.

A vicon system will be used by the researcher for kinematic analysis of the golf swing. Joint angles at the wrist and elbow on completion of the backswing will be calculated. The difference in the joint angles of the testing sessions will be compared. A full body marker set will be used.

Purpose of the study:

To determine if training aids and equipment can aid injury prevention by altering the biomechanics of the golf swing.

Equipment used:

Several resources are required to conduct this study successfully. To conduct each golf shot effectively, three five irons with an undersize, standard and oversize golf grips are required. Three golf training aids will be tested, these are SKLZ power wedge, tactic elbow swing trainer, these will be tested of the golf swing and the SKLZ refiner putter will be tested on components of putting. A driving net and foam golf balls are also needed to complete the golf shot. Participants will also be required to wear golf like comfortable clothing and shoes when partaking in the testing.

Electromyography (EMG) testing equipment will be required to calculate muscle activity in four forearm muscles. The electrodes will be places directly on the belly of the muscle. EMG electrodes will also be placed on the cervical, thoracic and lumbar sections of the spine.

A vicon system will be used to capture the swing. A series of high resolution cameras will be placed around the laboratory. Small spheres covered with a retro-reflective substance will be placed in strategic locations on the subject. Specifically, 14mm retro-reflective markers will be attached to the joints using hypoallergenic double sided tape. Specialised software will locate the markers seen through the cameras. The markers are then recorded as 3D coordinates. The collected marker data over time creates motion data.

8	How has the scientific quality of the research been assessed?														
	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 80%;">Independent external review</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Review within a company</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Review within a multi-centre research group</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Review within the Chief Investigator's institution or host organisation</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Review within the research team</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Review by educational supervisor</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other (please detail)</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </table>	Independent external review	<input type="checkbox"/>	Review within a company	<input type="checkbox"/>	Review within a multi-centre research group	<input type="checkbox"/>	Review within the Chief Investigator's institution or host organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	Review within the research team	<input type="checkbox"/>	Review by educational supervisor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other (please detail)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Independent external review	<input type="checkbox"/>														
Review within a company	<input type="checkbox"/>														
Review within a multi-centre research group	<input type="checkbox"/>														
Review within the Chief Investigator's institution or host organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>														
Review within the research team	<input type="checkbox"/>														
Review by educational supervisor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>														
Other (please detail)	<input type="checkbox"/>														

9	<p>Is the power of the study sufficient to answer the question that is being asked? Please indicate the power calculations used for the required sample size, including any assumptions you may have made. If you consider that power calculations are not appropriate, please explain why.</p> <p>Descriptive statistics will be applied to this study. At the moment no pilot studies have been carried out to incorporate in the power calculation. Based on a similar study in the literature we feel 15 participants will be adequate to establish statistical significance in the area of testing golf equipment.</p>
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10	<p>What statistical tests will you apply?</p> <p>Descriptive statistics and ANOVA will be performed to establish if there are changes with respect to using different grip sizes. The kinematic, kinetic and EMG data will be compared to establish if there are differences between the two upper limb training aids. The lower limb training aid will be evaluated by comparing two scenarios – with and without using the lower limb training aid. A t-test will be incorporated to establish significant differences between both testing scenarios. A t-test will also be incorporated to establish differences in force magnitudes with respect to the ultrasound outcome measures and the other biomechanical outcome measures.</p>
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11	<p>Does the research involve any physically invasive procedures? Are there any known hazards associated with these procedures?</p> <p>Before any participation from the subjects they will have to go through a PAR-Q to determine if they are able to take part in the study.</p> <p>There are no risks or hazards associated with this evaluation. A risk assessment form is included with this application (Appendix IV)</p>
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12	<p>Will individual or group interviews/questionnaires discuss any topics or issues that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting, or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could take place during the study (eg during interviews/group discussions or use of screening for drugs)</p> <p>N/A</p>
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13	<p>(a) Does the research involve any deception regarding aims and objectives?</p> <p>N/A</p> <p>(b) Will the research participants be debriefed? When? How? By whom?</p> <p>On completion of the experiment, the participants will be given a feedback sheet to complete. They will be given the freedom to express their experience and expand their views on the study. This feedback sheet will be done anonymously so that there is no pressure put on the subjects.</p>
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14	<p>What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?</p> <p>Two days of testing over a 6 week period.</p>
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15	<p>How will potential participants in the study be (i) identified, (ii) approached and (iii) recruited?</p> <p>(i) The subjects will be identified with their golfing background.</p> <p>(ii) Information sheets will be given to each potential participant over a two week period.</p> <p>(iii) The interested subjects will then be screened with a PAR-Q and this will determine their inclusion or exclusion in the study. They will also be informed they have the right to withdraw at any stage without reason.</p> <p>(iv) Poster advertisements, message boards and social media will also be used.</p>
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16	<p>What measures have been put in place to ensure confidentiality of personal data? Give details of whether any encryption or other anonymisation procedures will be used and at what stage.</p> <p>All data from PAR-Qs, consent forms and feedback sheets will be placed in password protected computers and a locked filing cabinet in the University of The West of Scotland. All subjects in the study will be informed who has access to these files and where they are kept. Also the graphs and tables for the data analysis will be recorded as subject 1, subject 2 and so forth. Video footage will also be secured on a password protected computer. The files on the camera will then be deleted. Subjects can locate their data on request to identify their own recordings. After completion of the study all appropriate data will be presented to the University of The West of Scotland.</p>
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17	<p>Who will have access to the data and what steps will be taken to ensure data remains confidential?</p> <p>The data will be placed in an electronic computer in the university grounds with a protective password and only the researcher and supervisor will have access to this code. Any feedback and consent forms will be filed in the supervisor's locked filing cabinet. This can only be accessed by the supervisor themselves.</p>
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18	<p>What is the potential for benefit to research participants?</p> <p>The study participants will leave the study with valuable experience in using high spec equipment and see the benefits training aids can have on performance.</p>
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19	<p>Will informed consent be obtained from the research participants?</p> <p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>If yes, give details of who will obtain consent and how it will be done. Give details of any particular steps to provide information (in addition to a written information sheet) eg videos, interactive materials. Please note that a copy of the subject information sheet must be included with this application.</p> <p>Refer to consent form (Appendix)</p> <p>If consent is not to be obtained, please explain why not.</p>
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20	Will a signed record of consent be obtained?
	Yes

21	How long will the participant have to decide whether or not to take part in the research?
	72 hours

22	Will subjects be informed that they can withdraw at any time from the study?
	Yes, both verbally and via written participation information sheet

23	Will the participants be from any of the following groups?
	Children under 16 <input type="checkbox"/>
	Adults with learning disabilities <input type="checkbox"/>
	Adults who are unconscious or severely ill <input type="checkbox"/>
	Adults with a terminal illness <input type="checkbox"/>
	Adults in emergency situations <input type="checkbox"/>
	Adults with mental illness (particularly if detained under Mental Health Legislation) <input type="checkbox"/>
	Adults with dementia <input type="checkbox"/>
	Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves <input type="checkbox"/>
	Those who could be considered to have a particularly dependent relationship with the investigator, eg those in care homes, medical students <input type="checkbox"/>
	Other (please detail) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

	<p>Please justify their inclusion.</p> <p>The selection process will be based on the individual's ability to play golf and are over 18 years of age. The subjects will be male.</p>
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24	<p>Are there any special pressures that might make it difficult for people to refuse to take part in the study (eg the potential participants are students of the investigator)?</p> <p>No</p>
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25	<p>Will the study result in financial payment or payment in-kind to the applicants/to the department? Please specify amounts etc involved.</p> <p>No</p>
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26	<p>Where will this research take place?</p> <p>The research will take place in the biomechanics laboratory located in the Hamilton campus.</p>
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27	<p>How are the costs of this study to be met?</p> <p>No cost are attached to the study</p>
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28	<p>Please describe any other ethical considerations which need to be taken into account by the Ethics Committee?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">No</p>
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Please indicate which documents are enclosed with this application:	
Subject/patient/participant information sheet/leaflet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Consent form	<input type="checkbox"/>
Copy of protocol	<input type="checkbox"/>
Letters to participant	<input type="checkbox"/>
Letter to parents/guardians/gatekeepers etc	<input type="checkbox"/>
Letter of ethical committee approval or other approvals	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other relevant materials (please indicate)	<input type="checkbox"/>

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the notes to investigators and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of subjects/study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signature of Principal Investigator: G Sorbie

Date: 27/02/14

Signature of Supervisor/

Director of Studies (if applicable): UC Ugbolue

Date: 27/02/14

8.9. Appendix 9

Summary of all Means with Output Differences Between Practice and Fatigue.

		:LAnkleAngles			:LHipAngles			:LKneeAngles			:LPelvisAngles			:RAnkleAngles			:RHipAngles			:RKneeAngles			:RPelvisAngles		
		X deg	Y deg	Z deg	X deg	Y deg	Z deg	X deg	Y deg	Z deg	X deg	Y deg	Z deg	X deg	Y deg	Z deg	X deg	Y deg	Z deg	X deg	Y deg	Z deg	X deg	Y deg	Z deg
Address	Mean DR Prac	9.05	2.46	23.93	41.65	-14.99	13.03	21.43	4.73	14.04	33.71	23.85	77.39	15.47	-5.19	6.17	32.13	-29.44	-7.13	24.72	-4.30	9.66	-35.90	-3.58	-57.02
	Mean DR Fat	3.30	-1.84	6.39	25.32	-13.16	-3.40	17.83	5.19	-2.01	15.58	18.77	51.10	2.79	1.39	-6.23	24.21	-22.68	-7.09	18.86	4.47	8.62	8.85	-8.89	-41.22
	Difference	5.75	4.30	17.53	16.33	-1.83	16.43	3.60	-0.46	16.06	18.13	5.08	26.28	12.68	-6.58	12.40	7.93	-6.77	-0.04	5.86	-8.77	1.04	-44.75	5.30	-15.80
	Mean 7I Prac	5.98	-1.46	4.96	31.76	-12.57	-4.57	21.15	5.85	-3.09	49.09	60.01	103.69	5.52	0.88	-3.37	47.43	-39.41	43.60	19.54	3.01	4.59	13.68	-7.28	-50.96
Mean 7I Fat	4.77	-1.91	5.50	32.51	-12.30	-2.83	20.92	6.40	-2.07	19.30	20.48	53.58	4.92	1.54	-5.87	30.98	-20.56	-3.91	22.28	3.04	7.22	12.30	-10.07	-43.17	
Difference	1.22	0.45	-0.54	-0.75	-0.27	-1.74	0.23	-0.55	-1.02	29.79	39.53	50.11	0.60	-0.66	2.50	16.45	-18.85	47.51	-2.74	-0.02	-2.64	1.38	2.79	-7.80	
Top of Backswing	Mean DR Prac	12.43	5.98	2.95	4.49	-45.88	2.59	41.23	8.08	9.84	29.80	21.77	122.23	7.29	-16.42	21.12	31.26	0.94	-1.80	22.34	-10.08	9.51	108.73	-22.02	-119.14
	Mean DR Fat	8.81	2.47	-9.89	9.89	-28.87	-15.73	30.49	9.21	-5.86	15.13	24.00	101.83	-2.70	-3.50	11.77	26.91	-1.79	15.44	18.95	-0.53	10.07	4.42	-8.00	-85.83
	Difference	3.62	3.52	12.84	-5.41	-17.01	18.31	10.74	-1.13	15.70	14.67	-2.23	20.40	9.99	-12.92	9.35	-4.35	-2.78	-17.34	4.30	-9.57	104.31	-14.03	104.31	-33.31
	Mean 7I Prac	13.01	1.80	-8.95	19.65	-31.16	-13.50	33.22	11.17	-3.79	35.96	39.36	111.64	-0.13	-2.65	8.78	34.70	-10.26	33.37	17.49	-0.45	5.81	14.44	-6.94	-79.22
Mean 7I Fat	11.48	2.13	-8.71	19.21	-33.05	-14.84	32.91	10.53	-6.24	19.62	17.62	87.43	0.16	-2.12	7.92	28.56	-2.61	6.95	21.69	2.90	11.41	13.44	-8.35	-78.15	
Difference	1.53	-0.33	0.36	0.44	1.89	1.34	0.31	0.63	2.45	16.34	21.74	24.21	-0.28	-0.53	0.85	6.15	-12.88	26.42	-4.20	-3.35	-5.60	1.00	1.40	-1.07	
Acceleration	Mean DR Prac	6.77	0.80	25.84	31.94	-6.18	11.11	25.40	4.60	19.68	33.03	21.01	51.95	5.88	-6.34	-8.04	13.03	-30.06	-12.21	34.00	-0.15	10.53	127.59	37.90	
	Mean DR Fat	0.66	-3.76	11.82	20.02	-3.00	-2.89	19.54	4.06	5.77	10.86	21.87	44.54	-2.16	4.44	-16.32	14.62	-24.77	3.15	22.84	2.60	4.96	0.04	-5.85	-28.53
	Difference	6.11	4.56	14.03	11.92	-3.18	14.00	5.86	0.55	13.91	22.17	-0.85	7.41	8.04	-10.77	8.28	-1.60	-5.29	-15.36	11.16	-2.75	5.57	3.97	133.44	66.43
	Mean 7I Prac	6.21	-3.18	8.85	26.34	-4.37	-4.39	25.66	5.53	3.78	31.83	39.99	69.37	1.04	3.39	-12.40	29.60	-31.10	28.63	24.77	1.40	3.87	9.70	-6.97	-36.34
Mean 7I Fat	1.00	-3.79	11.51	25.38	-2.98	-3.81	21.74	5.60	6.48	13.86	17.46	38.68	1.33	4.32	-15.83	18.23	-26.20	-1.45	27.84	4.25	6.59	7.74	-8.24	-29.46	
Difference	5.21	0.60	-2.67	0.96	-1.39	-0.58	3.91	-0.07	-2.70	17.97	22.53	30.69	-0.29	-0.93	3.43	11.37	-4.90	30.07	-3.08	-2.84	-2.72	1.96	1.28	-8.88	
Impact	Mean DR Prac	-0.89	-1.60	33.99	23.81	16.45	15.24	15.67	4.93	16.99	23.66	20.03	39.22	1.18	-4.66	-12.37	-0.11	-33.04	-15.98	32.64	1.38	11.74	-6.26	-7.71	6.65
	Mean DR Fat	-6.72	-6.59	20.49	10.30	3.13	-2.47	11.77	4.17	3.57	7.10	22.61	33.66	-6.90	6.09	-21.57	2.54	-26.01	0.45	21.21	3.03	5.38	-3.93	-6.38	-14.43
	Difference	5.84	4.99	13.50	13.50	13.32	17.71	3.90	0.76	13.42	16.55	-2.58	5.56	8.08	-10.75	9.20	-2.65	-7.03	-16.44	11.43	-1.65	6.37	-2.32	-1.33	24.08
	Mean 7I Prac	0.60	-5.50	15.67	17.45	2.32	-4.43	19.07	5.24	2.45	28.32	40.50	60.50	-2.18	4.69	-16.37	19.87	-34.66	25.37	24.44	1.17	4.75	6.02	-7.30	-27.30
Mean 7I Fat	-4.95	-6.85	20.00	15.76	2.66	-3.07	13.78	6.78	3.24	10.16	18.50	28.10	-2.03	5.64	-19.92	7.12	-29.11	-6.68	26.19	4.10	7.13	4.06	-9.30	-18.89	
Difference	5.55	1.35	-4.33	1.69	-0.35	-1.36	5.29	-1.54	-0.79	18.16	22.00	32.40	-0.15	-0.94	3.55	12.75	-5.55	32.04	-1.76	-2.92	-2.38	1.96	1.99	-8.41	
Early follow through	Mean DR Prac	-3.17	-3.04	38.62	9.62	10.68	12.22	6.17	13.62	16.21	19.62	30.25	-2.52	-3.74	-14.88	-9.64	-31.48	-17.25	28.13	-2.52	8.16	114.34	-1.03	127.59	37.90
	Mean DR Fat	-8.29	-8.11	25.09	3.29	5.35	0.50	5.98	4.57	1.24	4.32	22.52	23.37	-11.13	6.75	-24.05	-6.30	-22.37	-0.15	21.59	3.10	6.38	-6.69	-6.31	-7.15
	Difference	5.11	5.07	13.53	6.33	5.33	16.33	2.64	1.60	12.38	11.89	-2.91	6.88	8.61	-10.48	9.16	-3.34	-9.11	-17.10	6.54	-5.62	1.78	121.03	-91.44	-19.33
	Mean 7I Prac	-3.20	-8.52	24.47	8.96	7.35	-1.72	14.44	5.53	-2.06	24.14	39.88	47.13	-5.54	6.06	-21.36	9.68	-35.00	22.67	26.11	0.59	5.93	2.51	-6.85	-14.10
Mean 7I Fat	-6.74	-8.54	25.43	6.52	7.14	-0.28	9.59	6.91	0.65	7.11	18.90	15.56	-6.82	7.10	-25.00	-3.47	-28.79	-7.33	27.98	3.60	7.84	1.07	-9.76	-6.42	
Difference	3.55	0.02	-0.96	2.44	0.21	-1.44	4.85	-1.38	-2.71	17.53	20.98	31.57	1.28	-1.04	3.64	13.15	-6.21	29.99	-1.86	-3.01	-1.91	1.44	2.91	-7.68	
Late follow through	Mean DR Prac	-3.27	-9.36	54.77	12.39	13.34	30.43	17.40	2.72	15.18	28.13	18.52	-12.15	-11.54	-6.72	-2.06	-16.31	-17.55	-20.61	24.69	-1.49	6.26	-3.83	-8.47	37.74
	Mean DR Fat	-9.76	-15.15	40.66	3.17	9.53	11.61	7.47	1.41	4.22	10.95	20.54	-16.32	-23.03	5.36	-17.18	-13.63	-6.39	0.36	17.59	5.80	9.54	-0.93	-3.18	33.69
	Difference	6.49	5.79	14.11	9.22	3.80	18.81	4.92	1.31	10.96	17.17	-2.03	4.18	11.49	-12.08	15.13	-2.68	-11.16	-20.96	7.09	-7.28	-3.27	-2.90	-5.29	4.05
	Mean 7I Prac	-6.42	-14.37	41.29	5.34	9.49	10.57	11.56	1.38	-0.64	15.99	22.50	-10.19	-20.22	2.86	-9.79	-9.67	-18.73	1.08	21.96	3.67	7.03	5.19	-6.09	26.60
Mean 7I Fat	-8.76	-14.09	38.47	4.82	7.22	10.41	10.42	2.06	5.04	12.20	15.29	-25.93	-21.44	3.22	-11.21	-12.36	-9.46	-7.50	24.63	7.13	10.06	5.47	-5.34	35.88	
Difference	2.34	-0.28	2.83	0.51	2.27	0.16	1.14	-0.68	-5.69	3.79	7.21	15.74	1.22	-0.36	1.42	2.68	-9.28	8.59	-2.67	-3.46	-3.04	-0.28	-0.75	-9.28	

8.10. Appendix 10

Table of T-Tests Pre Versus Post Fatigue

Phase	Club	LAnkX	LAnkY	LankZ	LHipX	LHipY	LHipZ	LKneeX	LKneeY	LKneeZ	RAnkX	RAnkY	RankZ	RHipX	RHipY	RHipZ	RKneeX	RKneeY	RKneeZ
Address	Driver	0.29	0.17	0.17	0.05	0.26	0.36	0.15	0.99	0.36	0.06	0.61	0.18	0.17	0.28	0.95	0.27	0.37	0.31
Address	7 Iron	0.48	0.51	0.74	0.52	0.90	0.39	0.82	0.42	0.58	0.97	0.12	0.17	0.11	0.12	0.10	0.18	0.86	0.14
Top of Backswing	Driver	0.37	0.09	0.33	0.76	0.09	0.28	0.01	0.91	0.36	0.10	0.16	0.20	0.27	0.76	0.18	0.33	0.27	0.87
Top of Backswing	7 Iron	0.08	0.87	0.82	0.19	0.60	0.93	0.16	0.06	0.20	0.85	0.31	0.46	0.10	0.14	0.19	0.52	0.31	0.20
Acceleration	Driver	0.20	0.19	0.21	0.08	0.15	0.37	0.05	0.15	0.38	0.28	0.22	0.40	0.93	0.23	0.19	0.09	0.78	0.23
Acceleration	7 Iron	0.01	0.88	0.68	0.05	0.49	0.34	0.00	0.40	0.72	0.89	0.34	0.43	0.05	0.35	0.16	0.83	0.39	0.52
Impact	Driver	0.28	0.18	0.22	0.16	0.29	0.26	0.21	0.18	0.42	0.33	0.22	0.37	0.75	0.15	0.18	0.14	0.88	0.26
Impact	7 Iron	0.01	0.67	0.59	0.06	0.97	0.13	0.00	0.37	0.94	0.91	0.39	0.50	0.05	0.29	0.14	0.92	0.38	0.61
Early follow through	Driver	0.39	0.20	0.19	0.12	0.22	0.29	0.36	0.04	0.47	0.34	0.22	0.39	0.66	0.06	0.16	0.23	0.50	0.41
Early follow through	7 Iron	0.18	0.52	0.65	0.12	0.73	0.22	0.00	0.26	0.68	0.62	0.29	0.44	0.08	0.23	0.16	0.91	0.36	0.71
Late follow through	Driver	0.30	0.31	0.12	0.06	0.27	0.18	0.11	0.22	0.52	0.44	0.16	0.18	0.65	0.07	0.12	0.17	0.32	0.44
Late follow through	7 Iron	0.49	0.38	0.08	0.57	0.15	0.36	0.23	0.52	0.41	0.90	0.60	0.62	0.77	0.05	0.62	0.66	0.30	0.49

Table of T-Tests by Club

Phase	Fatigue Status	LAnkX	LAnkY	LankZ	LHipX	LHipY	LHipZ	LKneeX	LKneeY	LKneeZ	RAnkX	RAnkY	RankZ	RHipX	RHipY	RHipZ	RKneeX	RKneeY	RKneeZ
Address	Practice	0.50	0.20	0.14	0.19	0.16													